

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D 4.3

Report on simplified models for the estimation of seismic functional and systemic losses

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Uice	Haskoli Islands (University of Iceland)	Iceland
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GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description

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1 INTRODUCTION

The WP4 objective is to develop a procedure for the rapid prediction of losses immediately following an earthquake, while accounting for field observations and structural monitoring to update the loss models to be included in the TURNkey FWCR platform. This framework is articulated in two main components, of which the first is the development of predictive models for the vulnerability and loss estimation of exposed assets. This component includes the physical vulnerability of single elements, as well as the systemic vulnerability and functionality loss of interconnected infrastructure, due to the importance of the latter when conducting rapid response operations. The models are selected on the basis of their applicability/usability with reference to the Test Beds (TBs). The objective is to improve existing models with a focus on simplicity and applicability for various types of exposure data and to harmonise the input-output data for use on the TURNkey FWCR platform. The present deliverable, companion to deliverable D4.2, collects specifically literature and documentation relevant to the definition of functionality losses for the systems present in the TBs of the TURNkey project. It also shows how such models are used within the TBs.

In section 2 information is arranged by structural typology, infrastructure typology, and use of the infrastructure while a separate subsection reviews the specific work applicable at the infrastructure system level. Section 3 exemplify the application to the specific TB. It should be noted that given the nature of the TBs and the planned work in relation to them, structural and infrastructural typologies are only specific to one or two TBs, and not all TBs have focused their work on studying the specific functionality losses of the infrastructure pertaining to their site.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW ON FUNCTIONALITY LOSS MODELS

The existing literature on functionality loss models is classified at three levels: frameworks for the quantification of the functionality loss of infrastructures localized in a small area (section 2.1), frameworks for the quantification of the functionality loss at individual-object level in case of infrastructures including multiple physical assets and networks (section 2.2) distributed over larger surfaces, and frameworks for the quantification of functionality loss at system level in case of infrastructures including multiple physical assets and networks (section 2.3) of different nature. For each of the three classes, the following information is collected in a tabulated format: Reference, Methodology applied in the study, Object to which the function is applicable, Type of function used to describe the loss, Indicators used to describe the loss, Critical component whose measured response determines the functionality loss of the structure. At the system level, Interdependencies with other network/systems and organizational issues are also highlighted, if considered in the study. This classification is similar to the classification in Deliverable 4.2 and allows for inclusion of the relevant framework or model in the FWCR platform.

2.1 Functionality loss models of infrastructures composed by single physical asset

This section reviews the state-of-the-art on functionality assessment frameworks following earthquake hazards for Critical Infrastructures (CIs) localized in a confined area, such as hospitals and schools, made up of a modest number of assets. In this context CIs are defined as indicated by the European Council in 2004 (European Council, 2008). In most cases this kind of infrastructures are constituted either by a single physical

asset, or by multiple assets on the same compound, but largely independent (although some services and lifelines might be linked to a common plant)

The loss of functionality of CIs localized in a small area is based on a single value of the earthquake intensity measure, unlike the loss of functionality of networked CIs including multiple physical assets and networks extended over large regions, such as roads or other linear infrastructure. In the immediate aftermath of an earthquake, in the case of isolated infrastructure first responders are called to only one location. Moreover, activity relevant to earthquake early warning (EEW) and rapid response (RRE) will be focused to a specific asset. The loss of functionality of a hospital, for instance, can result also in delays of rescue operations conducted on other infrastructures or building stock therefore the cascading effects of functionality losses of such infrastructure, should be considered for a complete analysis at urban or regional level.

For this kind of CIs the overall functionality can be dependent on the functionality of the building, but also its service lines, the functionality of fittings, equipment and the availability of personnel. In the following subsections specific functionality loss function for school and hospital infrastructure are considered separately.

2.1.1 Schools

A relatively large number of studies exist in literature which assess the seismic vulnerability of existing school constructions and determine the expected annual losses with respect to probabilistic hazard models. Among those D'Ayala et al. (2020) have developed a taxonomy system and corresponding vulnerability functions applicable at global level, based on a large database across a number of countries worldwide (see the GLOSI, World Bank 2020,). The GLOSI project considers a large number of typologies in unreinforced and reinforced masonry, confined masonry (Vatteri & D'Ayala, 2021) and reinforced concrete. The GLOSI models stores a library of vulnerability functions, which can be used to estimate Expected Annual losses (EAL) in both economic and casualty terms, once the specific hazards IM and the specific exposure portfolio at a particular location are determined. Nassirpour et al. (2018) have developed a tool for rapid visual multi-hazard vulnerability prioritization of school infrastructure against earthquake, typhoon, and flood. The tool expedites the process of identifying the most vulnerable school buildings within a large portfolio for further decision-making. For each considered school, a set of parameters, including general information on the building and its occupants, structural and non-structural characteristics, and secondary vulnerability modifiers, are collected, and scored to determine a vulnerability index for each considered school building exposed to each of the hazards. The applicability of the proposed methodology is tested by assessing 115 elementary schools in a city of the Philippines. The ranking of schools by vulnerability allows prioritization of interventions. Following up from the previous studies, D'Ayala et al (2021) using the screening procedure described in Nassirpour et al. (2018) have identified as vulnerable to seismic hazard a number of asset typologies in the Philippine school portfolio. These are classified using the GLOSI taxonomy and their analytical fragility and vulnerability is determined using the approach described in D'Ayala et al (2020). The need for retrofitting is highlighted and the reduction in vulnerability and loss is measured by comparing losses for the unretrofitted and retrofitted index buildings.

Other studies such as O'Reilly et al (2018) have considered case studies, in this case typical of the Italian school portfolio in reinforced concrete, and have determined EAL and collapse safety. Detailed numerical models were developed using information collected during in-situ inspections in order to accurately represent the dynamic response of the school structures. To estimate economic losses, a structural and non-structural element inventory was compiled using in-situ survey information. However, the loss of function was not considered. The work presented by Perrone et al. (2020) analysed a stocks of school buildings in order to identify features typical of three different structural typologies. Six typical buildings were selected, two

building for each typology. The authors carried out an inventory of non-structural elements, fittings, services and equipment. The inventory was used together with the fragility functions and Mean Annual Frequency of Exceedance of seismic intensity to calculate the Expected Annual Losses using the procedure proposed by FEMA P-58 (FEMA, 2018) based on the two lowest Limit States and the estimated losses.

The previous model assessed loss of functionality based on the physical asset of the school, the “hard” part of the school. On the contrary, Hassan et al. (2020) proposed a method that included also the “soft” component of the infrastructure “school”, i.e. the human resources. This assessment is based on a “success tree”. Some of the indicators used in the study proposed by Hassan et al. (2020) (supplies, staff and accessibility) will be used for one of the CIs tools proposed in D5.2 and tested in the testbeds.

Table 2-1: Existing functionality loss models for schools in the literature.

Reference	Methodology	Functions	Object	Indicators	Critical components	Classification
D’Ayala et al (2020)	Analytical Fragility and Vulnerability functions	Mean damage ratio	Masonry and RC School Buildings	EAL	Structural and non-structural elements Drift of structural elements	●
Nassirpour et al. (2018)	Empirical Vulnerability index For multi-hazard	Vulnerability index	School buildings , various typologies	Vulnerability scores	Structural, non-structural elements and fittings	●
Vatteri and D’Ayala (2021)	Analytical Fragility and Vulnerability functions	Mean damage ratio	Confined Masonry Buildings	Mean damage ratio	Structural elements.	●
GLOSI World Bank (2019)	Analytical Fragility and Vulnerability functions	Mean Damage Ratio	Masonry and RC School buildings	EAL	Structural and non-structural elements Drift of structural elements	●
D’Ayala et al. (2021)	Analytical Fragility and Vulnerability functions	Mean Damage ratio	RC School buildings	Mean damage ratio	Structural and non-structural elements Drift of structural elements	●
O’Reilly et al. (2018)	Analytical Fragility and Vulnerability functions	Expected annual losses	School Buildings	Direct losses	Drift: R/C Columns, Joints, Masonry Infills, Partitions, Doors, Windows, Desks, Chairs Chord Rotation: Precast Columns, Masonry Piers and Spandrel Moment: Precast Panels PFA: Ceiling, Lighting, Piping, Bookcases, Blackboards, Electronic Hardware	●
Perrone et al. (2020)	Analytical Fragility and Vulnerability functions	Expected Annual Losses	Single school (only physical elements)	Expected Annual Losses Loss ratio of each of the four Limit States defined and Seismic class	Structural elements and non-structural elements (such as partition walls, doors, windows, furniture and electronic equipment), etc.)	●
Hassan et al. (2020)	Qualitative and quantitative Indexes	School system recovery	School system: more than one school including physical and soft elements	Expected total functionality of the education service. UNESCO service availability; quality of the education providers	Structural elements, non-structural elements, lifelines and internal services, staff	●

Classifications (concerning the applicability to RRE):

- ✓ Directly applicable
- Not directly applicable
- ✗ Not applicable

2.1.2 Hospitals and healthcare facilities

The functionality of hospitals and other healthcare facilities is a critical element to ensure rapid response operations after an earthquake. Cimellaro et al. (2010) were among the first to propose a quantitative evaluation of disaster resilience of health care facilities. In this study the evaluation is based on dimensionless analytical functions related to the variation of functionality during a period of interest, including the losses in the disaster and the recovery path. This evolution in time differentiates the resilience approach from pure loss estimation and their momentary effects. The recovery process usually depends on available technical and human resources, societal preparedness, public policies and may take different forms, which can be estimated using simplified recovery functions or using more complex organizational and socio-political models. Losses are described as functions of fragility of systems that are determined using multidimensional performance limit thresholds. The proposed framework is applied to a typical Californian Hospital building considering direct and indirect losses in its physical system and in the population served by the system. This framework has been endorsed and followed by numerous studies. Most recent works in this field, worth of mention, are the one by Favier et al. (2019) which focused on determining the performance of an emergency department. The novelty of the proposed approach lies in the explicit integration of the inelastic structural and non-structural response of the building and damage with its loss of functionality, downtime, and emergency patient treatment rate. The functionality loss is expressed in terms of patient waiting time and this is directly correlated in a probabilistic framework to the earthquake intensity and the physical vulnerability of the non-structural contents of the hospital building. The functional downtime is obtained from HAZUS and from onsite survey following the 2010 Maule Chile and more recent events. The in-patient flow is also treated probabilistically and correlated with the seismic event intensity. Similarly, Ceferino et al. (2020), present a methodology to evaluate emergency response by assessing the loss of hospital functions and the flow and multi-severity injuries as a result of earthquake damage. The objective is to determine effective plans for patient transfers and allocation of ambulances and mobile operating rooms. This methodology is applied to Lima, Peru, subjected to a disaster scenario following a magnitude 8.0 earthquake. The spatial distribution of the hospital facilities is identified as a critical bottleneck in emergency treatment and therefore the need for modelling these as a connected system is recognised to improve and optimise emergency response at community level.

Hassan and Mahmoud (2019) modelled numerically the full seismic functionality and recovery process of a six-story hospital, located in Memphis, TN, including soil-structure interaction. The hospital functionality assessment encompasses both quantity and quality of the hospitalization service. The study also investigates the hospital dependence on five lifelines, including their interdependence. Recoveries of the different lifelines are estimated using continuous Markov chain process, where the community resources are distributed among the different lifelines using dynamic optimization to either obtain the most economic return for the whole community or the fastest recovery of the hospital. In addition, the effect of including infrastructure interdependence on the recovery of the hospital is evaluated.

Yavari et al. (2010) used the collection of damage occurred in previous earthquakes to define performance levels of hospitals and healthcare facilities. In this study whilst the performance of structural, non-structural elements and lifelines were estimated through fragility functions; the performance of the “soft” component of the infrastructure, the personnel, was assessed by estimating its availability. The overall performance of the hospital was calculated through a functionality tree and the losses were estimated as the inverse of the functionality. Such study highlighted the importance of the “soft” component of every healthcare infrastructure. Other more recent studies consider also the importance of this component. The World Health Organization & Pan American Health Organization (2015) used answers to a questionnaire aggregated through weight to evaluate the overall performance through a Hospital Safety Index. Jacques et al.(2014), adopted the

same approach, but the data were aggregated through a fault-tree analysis and several hospitals were combined in networks. The use of questionnaire was also applied by Anhour and Miyajima (2020) , however they did not include the “soft” components of the healthcare infrastructure. A tool proposed in D5.2 will use an adapted version of the approach adopted by World Health Organization & Pan American Health Organization (2015) to assess the loss and resilience of infrastructures located in the TBs.

Table 2-2: Existing functionality loss models for hospitals in the literature.

Reference	Methodology	Function	Objects	Indicators	Critical components	Classification
Cimellaro et al. (2010)	Stochastic recovery functions	Analytical fragility function Loss functions	Medical services	Economic losses & recovery time	Concrete hospital buildings	●
Favier et al. (2019)	Discrete event simulation model	Piecewise affine function of ceiling failure to functionality loss	Medical services	Patient waiting times	Structural and non-structural elements	●
Hassan & Mahmoud (2019)	Markov chain process & dynamic optimization	Quantitative and qualitative functional losses Fault tree functions	Medical services	Hospital functionality	Buckling restrained braces, and connections	●
Ceferino et al. (2020)	Probabilistic earthquake simulation, Network flow model with an optimization formulation (strategies)	Hospital Safety Index	Single hospital (physical and soft elements) Emergency hospitals	Performance of high-coordination emergency policies in terms of waiting times and effective use of hospital resources	Multi-severity injuries Components damages	✓
Anhour & Miyajima (2020)	Score based on questionnaires with answers provided with Likert scale. A-posteriori study	Qualitative Hospital score	Single hospital and single healthcare facilities (only physical elements)	Hospital functionality	Structural members, Lifelines (Water and energy, gas, telecommunications), medical equipment	✓
Jacques et al. (2014)	Function based metric with loss assessed through a survey data analysed with a fault-tree analysis	Qualitative Function –based metric for hospital network	Hospital networks (physical and soft elements)	Losses of staff, structure and stuff	Structural members, non-structural components, equipment, availability of staff	✓
World Health Organization & Pan American Health Organization. (2015)	Aggregated index based on answers to survey	Qualitative Hospital Safety Index	Single hospital building (physical and soft elements)	Hospital functionality	Structural elements, non-structural elements (such as services and supplies), and functional elements (such as human resources, communication)	✓

Classifications (concerning the applicability to RRE):

- ✓ Directly applicable
- Not directly applicable
- ✗ Not applicable

2.2 Functionality loss models on the component-level of CIs

This section considers standalone buildings which are not classified as infrastructure, i.e. do not have societal function associated to them, as well as the components of horizontal CIs.

Overall, as seen in deliverable 4.1 the physical damage state of engineering structures with reference to relevant seismic intensity measures (*IMs*), is established using existing fragility databases. Such frameworks can serve as a baseline tool for *TURNkey* project, given their practicality and computational tractability, in particular, when the standalone structures (e.g. a variety of buildings in a neighbourhood or individual bridges within a road network) are of interest. These resources, frameworks and protocols for use, have been reported in deliverable D4.2. On the other hand, such frameworks are deficient, inasmuch as they do not often take the status of the other interconnected component across the network into account, when it comes to the *functional state* of the structures under consideration (e.g. the physical damage of the connected road may impair the functionality of the bridge of interest, even if the physical damage sustained by the bridge itself is largely minor or none). The functional state of elements, component of networks is particularly critical in the rapid response phase when infrastructures might see increased and different demand, generated by the damaging event.

Indeed, when the emphasis shifts from physical fragility to functional losses, then components that are typically overlooked in structural-damage oriented studies might become critical. Without losses of generality, for instance, most of the research on the seismic fragility of bridge structures is carried out with reference to the damage state of their pier members to assess their collapse risk. Such a paradigm can be somehow misleading, when it comes to the real-world seismic events, as the physical damage of some other structural members, such as decks or abutments, or the bearings, even if minor, can affect the functionality of the individual bridge and its accessibility, in a significant manner.

2.2.1 Buildings

2.2.1.1 Functionality loss models

In this section building are treated as component of the building stock and studies are collected which consider the loss associated with them, beyond the mere physical damage. Studies specifically devoted to functionality losses for this category are rare, as usually the functionality loss is meaningful in relation to a specific function the building host, such as schools or hospitals or industrial process, already reported in the previous section 2.1. However, there are quite a number of studies which approach the problem either in terms of life-cycle costs or expected annual losses, considering indirect as well as direct losses. While these studies might not be of immediate application in the test beds, they are directly related to the repository created in D4.2 and are of relevance to *TURNkey* end users.

Table 2-3: Existing functionality loss models for buildings in the literature.

Reference	Methodology	Function	Object	Indicators	Critical components
Wen & Kang (2001a,b)	Life-cycle and multi-hazard analysis	See table 2-4	Office Building	Structural Lifetime, Discount Rate, Deaths and Injuries Costs	Structural Members (IDR)
Kappos et al. (1998)	Life-cycle (remaining life)	See table 2-4	Dwellings, Offices, Hospitals	Cost of Damage vs. Repair & Indirect Costs (e.g., Value of Human Life)	R/C Members and Infill Walls (IDR)
Smyth et al. (2004)	Life-cycle cost analysis	See table 2-4	5-story Residential Building	Cost of Damage vs. Repair Costs	R/C Members (IDR)
Porter et al. (2004)	Expected annual Losses	See table 2-4	1 Hotel, 3 Undefined	Net Asset Value (net income for real estate investor minus seismic losses)	R/C and Steel Members (IDR)
Lagaros (2007)	Life-cycle cost analysis	See table 2-4	Undefined 4-story Building	Initial construction cost, direct and indirect losses	R/C Members and Infill Walls (IDR)

Reference	Methodology	Function	Object	Indicators	Critical components
Lagaros & Papadrakakis (2007)	PBEE and Multi-Objective Optimization	See table 2-4	Undefined 2-story Building	Initial construction cost, damage of R/C members	R/C Members (IDR)
Lagaros et al. (2006)	Life-cycle cost analysis	See table 2-4	Generic 3-story Commercial Building	Initial construction cost, direct and indirect losses	R/C Members (IDR)
Kappos & Dimitrakopoulos (2008)	Life-cycle cost analysis	See table 2-4	Low-Rise Building Stock	Initial costs, direct and indirect losses (Strengthened vs. Original)	R/C Members (numerical and empirical vulnerability curves)
Lagaros et al. (2009)	Life-cycle cost analysis	See table 2-4	Undefined 2-Storey Building	Initial, direct and indirect losses	Structural and non-structural components, building content
Jaiswal et al. (2015)	Expected Annual Losses	See table 2-4	Building Stock in US	Direct economic losses (from Hazus)	Not Specified
Ramirez et al. (2012)	Life-cycle cost analysis	See table 2-4	30 Office Buildings (from 1-story to 20-stories)	Direct losses	R/C Beams-Columns (Deformation Damage Index), Column-Slab Connections & Drywall Partition, Finish, Glazing (IDR), Acoustical Ceiling, Sprinklers, Elevators (PGA)
Mitropoulou et al. (2010)	Life-cycle cost analysis	See table 2-4	5 and 8-story Buildings	Limit State Repair, Content Loss, Injury/Human Fatality, Rental, and Income Costs	R/C Structural (IDR), Non-Structural (PFA)
Ordaz et al. (2017)	Life-cycle cost analysis	See table 2-4	Low-Rise Reinforced Concrete Dwellings	Construction, Maintenance and Operation, Repair, Damage, and Failure Consequence (Revenue Loss, Deaths and Injuries)	Global assessment based on base shear demand
Martins et al. (2016)	Expected annual losses	See table 2-4	5 and 6-story RC Residential Buildings	Cost of Repair vs. Failure and Replacement	R/C Columns and Beams (Deformation Damage Index)
Ellingwood & Wen (2005)	Life-cycle cost analysis	See table 2-4	3-story Steel Moment Frame, 9-story Office, 2-story Masonry Res./Com. Building	Initial construction cost, direct and indirect losses	Resisting members (IDR)
Del Gobbo et al. (2017)	Expected Annual Losses	See table 2-4	16-Story Steel Office Building	Direct losses (per FEMA P-58)	IDR: Braced Frame, Facades, Partitions, Peak floor accelerations: Ceiling, Air Handling Unit, Electronics
Bal et al. (2008)	PBEE	See table 2-4	R/C and Masonry Building Stock	Damage and social Losses	R/C Members and Masonry infills (displacement demand/capacity)
Cardone & Perrone (2017)	Expected Annual Losses	See table 2-4	3 R/C Frame Residential Buildings	Direct losses (per FEMA P-58)	Frame Members, Masonry infills, Partitions (IDR), Roof Coverings, Chimneys, Lighting, Piping (PFA)
Cardone et al. (2019)	Expected Annual Losses	See table 2-4	8-story Existing Building	Initial retrofit cost and direct losses	Frame Members, Masonry infills, Partitions (IDR), Roof Coverings, Chimneys, Lighting, Piping (PFA)
Calvi (2013)	Expected Annual Losses	See table 2-4	4 and 7-Story R/C Frame Buildings	Repair and Replacement Costs, Downtime Consequences, Seismic Isolation and Retrofit Costs	Structural/Non-Structural Members (IDR), Non-Structural Members Only (PFA)
Manoukas & Athanatopoulou (2018)	PBEE	See table 2-4	3 Frame, Wall, and Dual Buildings	Construction, Repair, Loss of Contents, Rental and Relocation Costs	R/C Frame and Wall Members (IDR)
Letelier (2014)	Expected Annual Losses	See table 2-4	Office Buildings	Construction Cost and Annual Losses	Drift-Sensitive Structural and Non-Structural Members, Acceleration-Sensitive Non-Structural Members

Reference	Methodology	Function	Object	Indicators	Critical components
Vranes & Pielke Jr (2009)	Normalized Annual Losses	See table 2-4	Building Stocks	Property and Population Damage per Mitigation Cases	Not Available

2.2.1.2 Re-Interpretation of existing loss functions and models

This section assesses the applicability of the studies listed in Table 2-3 to Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE) and actions within the TURNkey project. The studies are classified according to the studied building types, building use, inputs, outputs, and applicability to testbeds. Table 2-4 shows the evaluation of the studies and the following are some key interpretations:

Statement 1 to the direct use of measurements:

The loss functions/models are not directly applicable because of the missing link with measured data (e.g. PGA) in the context of rapid response analysis.

Statement 2 to the input data:

The input in some of these models is related to the building response (e.g. inter-storey drift), and a link between the building response and the ground motion parameters is needed. In addition, numerical models are needed for the application of some of these models for the different types of buildings present in the testbeds.

Statement 3 to the output data:

The outputs related to the RRE is of main interest, and studies with indicators like expected annual losses or life-cycle costs are not of interest.

Statement 4 to the use of the functions for RRE:

The studies are classified according to their applicability to the TURNkey platform in the context of RRE and according to their inputs and outputs. The classification scheme is explained in the notes of Table 2-4.

Table 2-4: Assessment of existing functionality loss models for buildings in the literature (using Table 2-3)

No.	Reference	Building type/s	Usage	Input(s)	Output	Region of application	Classification	Comments
[1]	Wen & Kang (2001a,b)	S-M/H	COM	Sy	TELCC+ I&D, EFC+ I&D	USA	●	
[2]	Kappos et al. (1998)	RC1-L, RC3-L	RES, COM, HOS	I	BCR, DL, IDL	Greece	✓	
[3]	Smyth et al. (2004)	RC1-L, RC3-L (retrofitted)	RES	DGL	DL	Turkey	●	
[4]	Porter et al. (2004)	RC1-L, RC1-L (retrofitted), S-L	COM	Sa	EAL	USA and Japan	●	
[5]	Lagaros (2007)	RC1-H	U	IDR/DS	DL, IDL	Greece	●	
[6]	Lagaros & Papadrakakis (2007)	RC1-M	U			Greece	✗	No outputs related to losses
[7]	Lagaros et al. (2006)	RC1-L, RC1-M, RC1-H	COM	IDR/DS	DL, IDL	Greece	●	
[8]	Kappos & Dimitrakopoulos (2008)	RC-L	RES, COM	I	DL, IDL	Greece	✓	
[9]	Lagaros et al. (2009)	RC1-H	U	IDR/DS	DL, IDL	Greece	●	
[10]	Jaiswal et al. (2015)	Building stock	M			USA	✗	Only region specific
[11]	Ramirez et al. (2012)	RC1-H	COM	DDI/DS	DL	USA	●	
[12]	Mitropoulou et al. (2010)	RC1-M	U	IDR/LS, PFA/LS	LSR, CL, I&D, RC, IC	Europe	●	

No.	Reference	Building type/s	Usage	Input(s)	Output	Region of application	Classification	Comments
[13]	Ordaz et al. (2017)	RC1-M	RES	BSD	RL, I&D	Mexico and Colombia	●	
[14]	Martins et al. (2016)	RC1-L	COM	DDI	EAL, COR vs. COF	Portugal	●	
[15]	Ellingwood & Wen (2005)	S-M/H, M7	RES, COM	Sy	TC, DL, IDL	USA	●	
[16]	Del Gobbo et al. (2017)	S-M/H	U	IDR	DL	Europe	●	
[17]	Bal et al. (2008)	RC1-L, M6	M	IDR/DS	I&D	Turkey	●	
[18]	Cardone & Perrone (2017)	RC1-L	R	IDR/DS, PFA/DS	DL	Italy	●	
[19]	Cardone et al. (2019)	RC1-L	R	IDR/DS, PFA/DS	DL	Italy	●	
[20]	Calvi (2013)	RC1-L, RC1-L (retrofitted)	R	IDR/LS, PFA/LS	DL, IDL	Italy	●	
[21]	Manoukas & Athanatopoulou (2018)	RC1-L, RC2-M, RC3-M/H	U	IDR	DL, IDL	Greece	●	
[22]	Letelier (2014)	S-M/H	U	Sa	EAL	U	●	
[23]	Vranes & Pielke Jr (2009)	Building stock	U				✗	Not applicable

Explanations:

Building type/s:

Refer Table A4-4 in the deliverable report D4.1 (Schwarz et al., 2021).

Use:

COM – Commercial, RES – Residential, HOS – Hospital, U – Undefined, M – Mix

Input/s:

Sy - System yield force coefficient
I – Intensity (on the MMI scale)
DGL – Damage level
Sa – Spectral acceleration
IDR – Inter-storey drift

DS – Damage state
DDI - Deformation damage index
LS – Limit state
PFA – Peak floor acceleration
BSD – Base shear demand

Output/s:

TELCC – Total expected life-cycle cost
I&D – Injury and death
EFC – Expected failure cost
BCR – Benefit-cost ratios
DL – Direct losses
IDL – Indirect losses
EAL – Expected annual loss
LSR – Limit state repair

CL – Content loss
RC – Rental cost
IC – Income cost
RL – Revenue loss
COR – Cost of repair
COF – Cost of failure and replacement
TC – Total costs

Classifications (concerning the applicability to RRE):

✓ Directly applicable
● Not directly applicable
✗ Not applicable

Table 2-5: Inputs/output and corresponding reference number for functionality loss models in Table 2-3.

Output Input(s)	BCR	CL	COR vs. COF	DL	EAL	EFC + I&D	I&D	IC	IDL	LSR	RC	RL	TC	TELCC + I&D
BSD							[13]					[13]		
DDI			[14]		[14]									
DDI/DS				[11]										
DGL				[3]										
I	[2]			[2],[8]					[2],[8]					
IDR				[16],[21]					[21]					
IDR/DS				[5],[7],[9]			[17]		[5],[7],[9]					
IDR/DS, PFA/DS				[18],[19]										
IDR/LS, PFA/LS				[20]					[20]					
IDR/LS, PFA/LS		[12]					[12]	[12]		[12]	[12]			
Sa					[22],[4]									
Sy				[15]		[1]			[15]				[15]	[1]

2.2.1.3 Damage-consistent loss assessment

Suitable damage functions or so-called damage matrices are required to determine the financial losses due to earthquakes. These convert the determined structural damage (in form of damage grades/state) into a relative loss statement (damage rate or damage ratio - DR). The absolute financial loss is then determined from the DR and the replacement value of the structure.

The loss prediction is associated with great uncertainties, as there are only few reliable damage data sets available, besides data held by insurance companies, even in the international environment.

In the German Research Network on Natural Disasters (DFNK) a simple power function according to Eq. DR [%] = 0,969 · D_s^{3,0756} (2-1) was derived to determine the total loss for the city of Cologne (Schwarz et al., 2004) on the basis of damage ratios provided from a re-insurance company:

$$DR [\%] = 0,969 \cdot D_s^{3,0756} \quad (2-1)$$

DR Damage Ratio

D_s Calculated damage grades (here from simulation)

Further damage matrices can be found in the literature (including ATC-13; Whitman et al., 1973; Tyagunov et al., 2004; Penelis et al., 2002). They differ considerably with regard to the range of damage rates for the individual damage grades. The background for determining the damage rates in these matrices is usually not clearly described.

Damage matrices provides the possibility to determine a minimum, maximum or an average expected loss or can be used for a simulative loss modelling. Following the proposed ranges of damage rates (RDR) in these sources, three different variants (model 1 – model 3) are derived in (Maiwald & Schwarz 2020) and (Maiwald & Schwarz 2021) as basis for further study purposes (see Table 2-6). In addition, model 4 is defined as a next variant which implements a discussion initiated by (Maiwald & Schwarz 2019), recognizing the fact that buildings with damage grade D3, which are completely replaced after an earthquake, have to be categorized as a damage rate of 100%. Therefore, the maximum damage rates for damage grades D1 and D2 are increased. To quantify the uncertainties, in Maiwald & Schwarz (2020 and 2021) the relative losses following a beta (β) distribution are simulated using a mean value of 50% and a standard deviation of 20% based on the associated scatter of the ranges of damage rates (RDR) for the respectively determined damage grades D_s. The observed losses of the Albstadt earthquake of 1978 could thus be well reproduced in Maiwald & Schwarz (2020 and 2021). In the publications mentioned, the models were used to predict the losses on the approx. 300,000 individual buildings in the city of Cologne, depending on various earthquake scenarios with different occurrence rates and compared with the results of the original DFNK study (Schwarz et al., 2004).

However, the models must also be validated on an international scale in other damaging events.

The Central Damage Factors given in Table 2-7 refer to publications which are contributing to the loss functions in the recent OpenQuake database. The ranges of the mean loss ratios (in the background) are somehow compatible to those which are defined as “models” in Table 2-6, i.e., the central value fits one of the models of Table 2-6.

The main difference lies in the target of the study. The ranges in Table 2-6 provide models for random simulations enabling the consideration of different shares of Damage Grades (as explained before). For practical use, Central Damage Factors as compiled in Table 2-7 might be applied in a simplified deterministic way.

Table 2-6: Variants of scatter of the damage rates according to (Maiwald & Schwarz 2020, 2021).

Damage Grade	Range of the applied damage rate [%]			
	Model 1 (Minimal)	Model 2 (extended)	Model 3 (Models 1+ 2)	Model 4 (Maximal extended Expert based)
D0	0	0	0	0
D1	0 - 1	0.3 - 5	0 - 5	0.3 - 25
D2	1 - 7.5	5 - 20	1 - 20	5 - 50
D3	7.5 - 20	20 - 60	7.5 - 60	20 - 100
D4	20 - 60	60 - 100	20 - 100	60 - 100
D5	60 - 100	100	60 - 100	100

Table 2-7: Variants of Central Damage Factors according to OpenQuake (GEM 2021)

Limit state	Mean loss ratio [%]			Damage Grade	Mean loss ratio [%]	
	Pasquale-Goretti (2001) ¹⁾	Pasquale-Goretti (2001) ²⁾	Pasquale-Goretti (2001) ³⁾		Durkal et. al (2006) ⁴⁾	Kappos et al. (2006) ⁵⁾
None	0.2	0.3	0.5	Grade 0	0	0
Slight	4.7	4.7	3.5	Grade 1	10	0.5
Moderate	8.0	21.8	14.5	Grade 2	20	5
Heavy	22.0	41	30.5	Grade 3	40	20
Very heavy	29.5	78.1	79.9	Grade 4	90	45
Collapse	80.4	81.4	80.6	Grade 5	100	80

Explanations:

¹⁾ Maximum-damage-vertical-structure, ²⁾ Mean-damage-building, ³⁾ Mean-damage-vertical-structure, ⁴⁾ Damage ratio, ⁵⁾ RC buildings.

2.2.1.4 From Mean Damage Grade to Loss: Basic elements of an intensity-based risk assessment procedure

For the study area of Central Europe, an intensity-oriented damage and loss prediction model has been developed and adapted to regional seismic risk studies in Germany (Schwarz et al., 2006a,b), Greece (Langhammer et al., 2006, Schwarz et al., 2017), Austria (Schwarz et al., 2007), and Switzerland (Schwarz et al., 2008, 2015). The procedures implemented in the model are structured in a modular system, and accordingly in a transparent way. Case studies for Central Europe are performed to calibrate the damage and loss model to the existing particularities of regional predominant building types (expressed by a Regionalization factor [Ri]). The scenarios refer to historical earthquakes in different Federal States of Germany (BW, NW, TH) as well as in Austria (A) and Switzerland (CH) (Schwarz et al. 2008).

Within the Geographical Information System (GIS)-based earthquake damage and loss prediction tools, the different data layers represent essential steps of the whole approach. Figure 2-1 illustrates the basic elements (modules) of an intensity-based earthquake model assuming the epicentre of a major historical event in Albstadt-Ebingen (referring to the Central European Earthquake from November 16, 1911).

The following explanations can be given:

(1) Shaking effects (intensities) describe the regional or local hazard [Is].

The intensity correction factors [ΔIs] accounts for the effect of local site conditions (subsoil, topography, deep geology; see [WP3.8]). Intensity correction factors are derived from different approaches including site

response studies as well as the statistical studies on the repeatedly observed shaking effects in differently sized raster elements.

(2) Mean Damage Grades $[D_m]$ are derived from local intensities using specifically elaborated damage functions and have to reflect regional differences in the building stock composition. [A regionalisation factor $[R_i]$ - as the key element for the damage prognosis - reflects the vulnerability of building types and leads to a modification of vulnerability functions.]

(3) Using correlations between the Mean Damage Grades $[D_m]$ and the Mean Damage Ratio $[MDR]$ the loss $[€]$ can be predicted for any value basis. The assets are taken from data provided by Bureaus for Statistics or authorized annual reports of socio-economic development.

According to the scheme in Figure 2-1 the following Vulnerability (VF) and Damage Functions (DF) have to be distinguished:

- Vulnerability Function (VF) of Type ① correlates the intensity with the Mean Damage Grade (D_m); Vulnerability is related to the level of earthquake resistance of the building or the building stock under consideration.
- Damage Functions (DF) of type ② tries to correlate the damage grade and the loss to building. An example is given by Schwarz et al. (2004, 2006b) for the case study of North Rhine Westphalia (NRW) as an outcome of the comprehensive risk project (German Research Network Natural Disasters - Deutsches Forschungsnetz Naturkatastrophen DFNK).
- Damage Functions (DF) of type ③ represents the re-insurance standard approach.

Figure 2-1: Basic steps and data layers of EDAC damage and loss assessment model (following the scheme presented for the model study Baden-Wuerttemberg by Schwarz *et al.*, 2006b)

Note: The example is illustrating the whole procedure for an earthquake in Germany with an epicentral intensity of $I_0 = 8.0$ close to the coordinates of the 1911 Central European Earthquake. The impact of soil conditions is not considered, i.e., an intensity correction is not applied.

2.2.1.5 Levels of elaboration

From an engineering point of view and with respect to damage prognosis four levels of elaboration and data processing can be distinguished and implemented into the damage and loss prediction tools:

- Address-orientated level: damage and loss description are related to individual buildings (or damage cases); any prognosis requires a nonlinear analysis and the prediction of the capacity curve of the main structural system.
- Micro-scale level: Damage Grades (D_i) according to EMS-98 (Grünthal et al., 1998) for all buildings of a city area or Mean Damage Grades (D_m) for a mesh of small sized raster elements have to be determined.
- For large scale damage and loss assessment models the meso- and macro-scale levels are appropriate and common practice. Therefore, the Mean Damage Grade (D_m) has to be determined for 5-ZIP code area elements, district elements or land-use areas (Figure 2-2c).
- The macro-scale level is preferred for (re-)insurance purposes and Probable Maximum Loss (PML) estimation; it is related to 2-ZIP code area elements (Figure 2-2d).

There is no problem to convert the results from the micro-to the meso- and macro-scale. The Mean Damage Grade (D_m) seems to be the representative parameter to reinterpret or to describe the damage situation.

[Note: Examples of damage scenarios and corresponding loss predictions are presented for the epicentres of major historical events in the D-A-CH States (Germany, Austria, Switzerland) by Schwarz et al. (2008). The examples are given for the Meso-scale level, i.e., the Mean Damage Grades (D_m) are determined for the district elements.]

Figure 2-2 Processing levels and parameters for damage and loss assessment (Schwarz *et al.*, 2006, 2015)

2.2.2 Bridges

Bridges are considered separately whether pertaining to the road network or the rail network as the functional losses are sensitive to different damage mechanism and represented by different indicators. The resulting methodologies and function developed are not interchangeable.

2.2.2.1 Highway bridges

This *Section* reviews the state-of-the-art on earthquake-induced functionality losses of bridge structures, which often serve as the most critical component of *Road Networks*. The present review encompasses work developed in the past 2 decades, which have developed relevant models based on the overarching framework of Performance Based Earthquake Engineering (*PBEE*).

Mackie and Stojadinovic (2006) examined the seismic behaviour of column members of typical concrete overpass bridges of highway networks, and then developed their seismic fragility model, which presents the exceedance probability of different Damage States (*DSs*) of those members, under different seismic Intensity Measures (*IMs*). Accordingly, they also computed the expected repair cost, with regard to each *DSs* of column members.

Based on *PBEE* as well, Conte and Zhang (2007) proposed a methodology which includes a probabilistic framework seismic hazard analysis, seismic demand analysis, capacity analysis, reliability/damage analysis, and loss analysis. The probabilistic seismic loss analysis is performed with a multi-layer Monte Carlo simulation approach. Accordingly, a seismic loss hazard curve, which indicates the mean annual rate of a decision variable exceeding a particular threshold value, can therefore be generated.

In real earthquake events, bridge structures might be damaged by the mainshock and also face potentially further damaging aftershock sequences. The allowable traffic on those bridges will thus become rather time-varying and stochastic, throughout the whole seismic events. To address such a challenge, Franchin and Pinto (2009) proposed a risk-based model as a viable tool for the decision-making on the allowable traffic with regard to those main shock-damaged bridges, based on the comparison between the structural collapse risk and the corresponding, tolerable risk level. Such model can be used within the rapid response analysis framework devised in D5.2.

As a follow-up and with the objective of accelerating the decision-making on the accessibility of main shock-damaged bridges in the context of aftershock sequences, Alessandri et al. (2013) developed a model combining the information derived from numerical analyses and the corresponding in-situ inspections. Besides, the risk, which a person living in an earthquake-prone region is exposed to during his/her life, has been proposed as an average annual risk. Such a new measure of risk was then employed as the criterion for the decision-making on the bridge accessibility, and was shown to be able to yield more nuanced and sensible decisions, compared with previous models. A similar approach is proposed within the *TURNkey* framework for selected monitored bridges.

Most recently, Gidaris et al. (2020) proposed a computationally tractable methodology, based on kriging surrogate model, for the probabilistic fragility and resilience analysis of bridge structures subjected to mainshock and aftershock sequences. The effect of aftershocks is explicitly considered by a simulation procedure of mainshock-aftershock sequences using stochastic ground motion modelling. As a strategy to reduce the computational costs associated with stochastic simulations, approximation of the nonlinear mainshock and aftershock bridge response is set to be obtained with the surrogate model established with respect to the uncertain hazard and structural model parameters, deterministic bridge and geometrical parameters, and the mainshock response. The proposed methodology is applied to the fragility and resilience assessment of a typical bridge class in California, exposed to seismic hazard that incorporates aftershock effects. The study demonstrates that those bridges exhibit increased vulnerability when aftershocks are taken into account. More importantly, aftershocks can have a further negative impact on the resilience of bridges, as they are found to be substantially delaying the post-shock recovery process.

In addition to the risk posed by the potentially damaging earthquakes, existing bridge structures of *Road Network* across earthquake-prone areas are also exposed to the risk due to the performance deterioration, in

the course of their life-cycles. To examine the functionality losses of aging bridges under seismic hazards, Ghosh *and* Padgett (2011) proposed a new approach, which incorporates the time-varying seismic vulnerability in the loss estimation via a framework based on a non-homogeneous Poisson process. Besides, the study also considered the correlation between components' damage to reach the total losses associated with the whole bridge system. Based on the corresponding case-studies, earthquake-induced functionality losses of bridge components are found to be substantially higher than that generated following time-invariant structural reliabilities.

In terms of socio-economic perspective, the repair time and repair cost associated with earthquake-damaged bridge structures also play a crucial role, in terms of the total loss estimation. Mackie et al. (2010) proposed a framework to enable the quantification on both the bridge repair cost and repair time. In such a framework, those two measures are obtained by linking the amounts of repair materials, to damage states requiring the repair, to structural response causing damage, and eventually to the intensity measures of the seismic hazard. Such a kind of disaggregation can come up with detailed information regarding the damage and the failure of specific bridge components, therefore allowing better decision-making regarding the design or the retrofit. In parallel, Decò et al. (2013) proposed a probabilistic model to estimate the repair time regarding earthquake-damaged bridges. Following such a model, the initial damage induced by earthquake hazards is characterized by fragility functions of the bridges of interest. To consider the adaptive repair pursuant to different levels of the initial damage and different pace of rehabilitation operations, a probabilistic six-parameter function (including residual functionality and idle time, etc.) was proposed, as a viable tool to evaluate the repair time needed for those bridges.

Karamlou and Bocchini (2017) proposed a new framework on the probabilistic restoration modelling of earthquake-damaged bridges. In such a framework, the restoration of bridges is shaped through a mathematical optimization, given the restoration tasks of its components, as well as a number of practical construction considerations and logistic constraints. The remaining functionality of bridge structures is determined from the restoration scheduled by taking into account a number of safety- and construction-induced traffic disruptions during the repair campaign. In addition, a simulation-based technique is proposed to quantify the probabilistic characteristics of the functionality, and particularly, to determine the probability bounds that would contribute to the informed decision-making on the post-shock emergency management, as well as the expeditious functionality loss estimation of those earthquake-damaged bridges.

When considering the whole life cycle of highway bridge structures, it is evident that they will be concurrently exposed to hazards other than seismic, during their life span, which might have shorter return periods, such as flooding or windstorms. Such hazards might be less damaging than earthquakes, but still significantly affect functionality. While this area of work is beyond the immediate remits of TURNkey, the approaches developed for the long-term functionality losses and resilience of bridge structures under combined natural hazards are relevant to the project and worth of review.

Argyroudis et al. (2020) developed an integrated framework for the quantitative resilience assessment of critical infrastructure systems, under multiple hazards, considering the vulnerability of the physical assets to hazard actions, the rapidity of the recovery, and the temporal variability of the hazards. The study proposes a well-informed asset resilience index, which accounts for the full, partial or no restoration of asset damage between consecutive hazard occurrences. The proposed framework is then applied to a typical highway bridge, which is exposed to multiple hazard scenarios, considering pragmatic restoration strategies. The case study highlights a profound effect of the occurrence time of the second hazard on the resilience index, and a considerable error with regard to the superimposition of resilience indices from different hazards, even if they have independent genesis.

Li et al. (2020) proposed an integrated framework for long-term resilience and loss assessment of highway bridges under multiple independent natural hazards, whereby the impacts of extreme events such as earthquakes, hurricanes and floods on the life-cycle performance of bridge structures can therefore be examined. A stochastic renewal process model of the random occurrence of hazard events is employed to investigate the expected long-term resilience and damage losses by considering both time-independent and time-varying occurrence characteristics. The proposed approach is applied to a bridge by considering the impacts of earthquake and hurricane hazards, and it was found that its long-term resilience associated with the earthquake with a 120-year return period is the lowest in the first 30 years.

Table 2-8: Existing functionality loss models for highway bridges in the literature.

Reference	Methodology	Functions	Object	Indicators	Critical components	Classification	Interdependencies of damage to other systems	Organisational issues
Mackie & Stojadinovic (2006)	PBEE	exceedance probability of different DSs	Overpass	Traffic capacity	Column	✓	Not considered	Not considered
Conte & Zhang (2007)	PBEE	mean annual rate	Bridge	Direct losses	Multiple components	●	Not considered	Not considered
Franchin & Pinto (2009)	Time-varying risk analysis	collapse risk vs. <i>The acceptable risk</i> corresponding,	Overpass	Accessibility	Column	✓	Not considered	Not considered
Alessandri et al. (2013)	Risk analysis	average annual risk	Overpass	Accessibility	Column	●	Not considered	Not considered
Gidaris et al. (2020)	Probabilistic restoration analysis	kriging surrogate model	Two span continuous RC box girder	Probabilistic distribution of functionality	Column	●	Not considered	Not considered
Ghosh & Padgett (2011)	Poisson process	time-varying seismic vulnerability	Overpass	Economic losses	Column	●	Not considered	Not considered
Mackie et al. (2010)	PBEE	Hierarchical, conditional probability functions	Overpass	Repair time	Column	✓	Not considered	Not considered
Deco et al. (2013)	Stochastic recovery function	Mathematical fitting	Overpass	Repair time	Multiple components	✓	Not considered	Not considered
Karamlou & Bocchini (2017a)	Resource constrained scheduling	Probabilistic bounds of functionality losses	Overpass	Restoration duration	Column	●	Not considered	Not considered
Argyroudis et al. (2020)	Probabilistic restoration analysis	resilience index	Bridge over river	Probabilistic distribution of functionality	Multiple components	●	Not considered	Not considered
Li et al. (2020)	Life-cycle and multi-hazard analysis	stochastic renewal process	Overpass	Economic losses	Column	●	Not considered	Not considered

Classifications (concerning the applicability to RRE):

- ✓ Directly applicable
- Not directly applicable
- ✗ Not applicable

2.2.2.2 Railway bridges

The literature review concerning railway bridges' functionality under earthquakes is dominated by the derailment phenomenon causing delays in the rail service, where the train loses contact with the rails due to the arrival of seismic waves on site. The state-of-the-art in derailment analysis relies on vehicle-bridge interaction (VBI) approaches (Yang & Wu 2002, Xia et al. 2006, Kim & Kawatani 2006, Tanabe et al. 2008, Du et al. 2012, Ju 2013, Montenegro et al. 2016, Jin et al. 2016, Wu et al. 2016, Yang et al. 2016, Zeng & Dimitrakopoulos 2017, Wang et al. 2020), a few others compress seismic derailment criteria into bridges' engineering demand parameters (EDPs) vis-a-vis specific intensity measures (Luo 2005, Guillaud 2006), and also there are examples utilising accident statistics (Uchiyama 2006). Concerning the VBI and EDP-based approaches mechanical models are developed to formulate the derailment problem for dynamic analysis (e.g., Tanabe et al. 2008, Wang et al. 2020), and those implementing accident statistics rely on databases from certain stakeholders and administrations (e.g., Uchiyama 2006).

In addition to the alternative formulations expressed above, there is a variation of parameters in terms of how the dynamic analysis is formulated: some propose standard uniform excitation for short-span structures (Luo 2005, Kim & Kawatani 2006, Fryba & Yau 2009, Ju 2013, Jin et al. 2016, Wu et al. 2016, Montenegro et al. 2016), whereas for long and multi-span systems, ground motion incoherency may play an important role in derailment factors (Xia et al. 2006, Tanabe et al. 2008, Du et al. 2012, Wang et al. 2020). Besides, some look into the derailment mechanics as a conceptual problem governed by a unidirectional phenomenon (e.g., Fryba & Yau 2009), whereas others study the combined effects of multiparameter and multi-directional aspects of the dynamic response of vehicle-bridge couple (e.g., Yang & Wu 2002). In general, the majority of the studies are centralised towards the binary status whether derailment occurs or not (e.g., Jin et al. 2016), whereas, there are examples extending the occurrence of derailment into its consequences, including monetary losses, downtime, and casualties (Uchiyama 2006).

Apart from the derailment problem, railway functionality related to bridge safety is also represented through probability of disconnection of origin-destination pairs (Misra & Padgett 2017) and is coupled with seismic risk minimization efforts conditioned to bridge retrofit decisions (Day & Barkan 2003). Therefore, there is a growing need for more studies addressing the end-user needs compatible with the actions to take in relation to post-event recovery and bridge resilience, showing a notable gap for railway bridge applications. Although the aforementioned VBI literature rigorously captures the physical background of train safety, there is a significant computational expense in the analyses depending on the detailing of the numerical models. Under circumstances where rapid outputs are needed such as early warning or post-event rapid response, one can compromise the complexity of the physics representation and rely on simplified formulations, given that the uncertainties are still incorporated into the simulation processes.

In TURNkey, the derailment problem is handled through multiparameter limit states paired with engineering demand parameters (see Guillaud 2006). Early warning actions maximizing railway bridge functionality and other consequences are established through fragility functions defining failure/survival conditioned to the intensity measure (Shinozuka et al. 2000), consequence models expressing costs and benefits of relevant actions (Cremen et al. 2020), decision analysis for the optimal risk-based action (analogous to Kameshwar et al. 2020), and assessing the system's contributions via the Value of Information (Wu et al. 2013). The proposed formulation is applied on a railway bridge in Luchon region at the French-Spanish border as part of the Testbed

2, with the aims of quantifying the early warning benefits in terms of various consequences such as downtime, casualties, and monetary losses under various derailment scenarios.

Table 2.9: Existing functionality loss models for railway bridges in the literature.

Reference	Methodology	Functions	Indicators	Critical components	Classification	Interdependencies of damage to other systems	Organisational issues
Yang et al. (2016)	Dynamic analysis on coupled train-bridge system	Railway serviceability	Maximum train speed	Tower and pier	●	Not considered	Not considered
Misra & Padgett (2017)	O-D analysis	Railway serviceability	Accessibility	Column	●	Not considered	Not considered
Yang & Wu (2002)	Dynamic analysis on coupled train-bridge system	Railway serviceability	Maximum train speed	Bridge and track structures	●	Not considered	Not considered
Day & Barkan (2003)	Decision trees and sensitivity analysis	Railway serviceability	Detour length, repair time, and costs	Inventory characteristics	●	Network performance	Not considered
Luo (2005)	Simplified analytical model	Railway serviceability	Acceleration response and spectral intensity	Pier, pile foundation, and soil	●	Not considered	Not considered
Xia et al. (2006)	Dynamic analysis on coupled train-bridge system	Railway serviceability	Maximum train speed (and support coherency)	Piers and girders	●	Not considered	Not considered
Kim & Kawatani (2006)	Dynamic analysis on coupled train-bridge system	Railway serviceability	Monorail system vs conventional	Steel piers and girders	●	Not considered	Not considered
Guillaud (2006)	Dynamic analysis and fragility curves	Railway serviceability	Maximum train speed (and support coherency)	Soil and structural properties	✓	Not considered	Not considered
Uchiyama (2006)	Consequence models and Monte Carlo simulation	Railway serviceability	Maximum train speed	Soil and structural properties	●	Not considered	Not considered
Tanabe et al. (2008)	Dynamic analysis on coupled train-bridge system	Railway serviceability	Demand parameters	Piers, steel box girders, and concrete slab	●	Not considered	Not considered
Fryba & Yau (2009)	Time history analysis under moving loads and earthquakes	Railway serviceability	Maximum train speed	Suspended structure	●	Not considered	Not considered
Du et al. (2012)	Dynamic analysis on coupled train-bridge system	Railway serviceability	Maximum train speed (and support coherency)	Truss girders, arches, and piers	●	Not considered	Not considered
Ju (2013)	Dynamic analysis on coupled train-bridge system	Railway serviceability	Derailment coefficient	Multi-span girder gaps, pier columns	●	Not considered	Not considered
Montenegro et al. (2016)	Dynamic analysis on coupled train-bridge system	Railway serviceability	Maximum train speed and track quality	RC columns	●	Not considered	Not considered
Jin et al. (2016)	Dynamic analysis on coupled train-bridge system	Railway serviceability	Wheel uplift	Deck and piers	●	Not considered	Not considered

Reference	Methodology	Functions	Indicators	Critical components	Classification	Interdependencies of damage to other systems	Organisational issues
Wu et al. (2016)	Dynamic analysis on coupled train-bridge system	Railway serviceability	Maximum train speed and vehicle types	Deck, pier, and pile foundations	●	Not considered	Not considered
Zeng & Dimitrakopoulos (2017)	Dynamic analysis on coupled train-bridge system	Railway serviceability	Contact detachment	Deck	●	Not considered	Not considered
Wang et al. (2020)	Dynamic analysis on coupled train-bridge system	Railway serviceability	Wheel-rail contact forces	Girders and piers	●	Not considered	Not considered

Classifications (concerning the applicability to RRE):

- ✓ Directly applicable
- Not directly applicable
- ✗ Not applicable

2.2.2.3 Tunnels

Table 2-10: Existing functionality loss models for tunnels in the literature.

Reference	Methodology	Functions	Indicators	Critical components	Interdependencies of damage to other systems	Organisational issues
Selva et al. (2013)	Bayesian approach	Metro line serviceability	Accessibility	shallow tunnels	Not considered	Not considered

2.2.2.4 Port facilities

A port is composed of interconnected structural and infrastructural elements that constitute a framework supporting the functionality of the entire multicomponent system. A variety of facilities exists within a seaport, such as wharf structures, infrastructure for cargo handling and storage, utility systems, such as electric power, etc. Potential disruptions of one element caused by a seismic event may trigger a domino effect that influences the performance of the entire system. According to the literature review (see Section 2.3.2.2), the functionality loss of a port in case of an earthquake should be evaluated by considering the port as a multi-component system. Therefore, individual component analysis for port facilities is not considered within TURNkey.

2.2.2.5 Sluices and channels

No relevant studies have been found on the seismic functionality assessment of sluices. The seismic performance of these structures is not widely studied in literature and fragility functions are not yet developed. In *TURNkey*, a location-specific damage assessment has been performed for the case of induced seismicity in the Groningen province (TB6) and the functionality assessment has then been estimated.

2.3 Functionality loss models at the system-level

This section reviews the state-of-the-art studies on the functionality assessment framework for individual CIs, following earthquake hazards. The value of these studies is their consideration of the effect of the interdependence among different CIs, on the functionality losses of those physical networks during the immediate response phase. However, it shall be noted the majority of those studies are scenario- and simulation-based, and thus somehow fall short, from the perspective of rapid loss estimation (*RLS*). To remedy such issue, a real-time data collection and processing framework is expected to be developed in *TURNkey*. In general, those data could be obtained with an array of different methods, like in-situ surveys, remote-sensors, crowdsourced traffic and incident data etc. Besides, such a framework is anticipated to be able to interpret the real-time data throughout the post-earthquake phases, with some statistical inference model, and thereby produce *RLS* and facilitate the corresponding decision-making.

2.3.1 Buildings

Table 2-11: Existing functionality loss models for building networks in the literature.

Reference	Methodology	Functions	Object	Indicators	Critical components	Interdependencies of damage to other systems	Organisational issues
Cavaleri et al. (2012)	Systemic loss analysis with MC simulations		Built areas	Usability / Habitability of buildings Nb of displaced people	Buildings	Water supply and Electric power systems	Not considered

2.3.2 Infrastructure systems

This section reviews the state of the art assessment framework for the functionality losses of different infrastructure networks under seismic hazard, on the system level.

2.3.2.1 Transportation systems

2.3.2.1.1 Road networks

This Section reviews state-of-the-art studies on the functionality losses of earthquake-damaged Road Networks, on the system level.

Sohn et al. (2003) studied the economic impact of earthquake hazards on road networks. Two aspects of cost are considered in their research, namely, the final demand loss and transport cost increase. The 1812 New Madrid earthquake is used to generate a scenario for the analysis. The developed model includes a transportation network loss function, a final demand loss function, and an integrated commodity flow model. The simulation results show that the road segments with more severe physical disruption are not necessarily the ones sustaining the most significant economic losses.

Kiremidjian et al. (2007) examined the functionality losses of road networks under damaging earthquakes. In the model they have proposed, the seismic behaviour of transportation networks is investigated from the perspective of both individual bridges, and the whole network. In particular, for networks, vehicle travel time is proposed as the primary measure on their functionality losses. Based on the case study on the road network across San Francisco Bay area, it was demonstrated that earthquake-induced liquefaction poses the most significant risk to bridge structures. The travel time of the network was evaluated regarding two different cases:

based on fixed or variable post-shock travel demand. For the first case, the total travel hours were found to increase in the post-earthquake repair phase, compared to the baseline network. For the second one, a lower traffic demand is assumed following observations on traffic patterns of past earthquakes in California. The corresponding total travel hours were shown to decrease indeed. However, they also noted that such an outcome may not hold true, for many road networks in other earthquake-prone areas, where the traffic demand may very likely increase following earthquakes, due to the different socio-economic contexts.

As a follow-up, Stergiou and Kiremidjian (2010) proposed a more comprehensive assessment model on seismic losses of road networks. In order to generate the informative and complete risk curves, more possible seismic scenarios will be included by that model. Meanwhile, in such a model, functionality losses are gauged by the lack of connectivity, reduction in traffic flow and increase in travel time. Accordingly, seismic risk is presented in terms of the annual rate of exceeding monetary losses. The model is applied to the road network of five counties in the San Francisco Bay Area, and the corresponding result reveals that the expected annual loss of the network reaches \$30.9 million. Furthermore, the outcome highlights that the operational economic losses can easily outweigh the structural value of bridges of the road network in that region.

Pinto et al. (2012) studied the functionality losses of road networks across earthquake-prone areas, based on connectivity loss. The study also takes into account the debris from collapsed buildings that might block some roads.

Argyroudis et al. (2015) established an integrated approach for the probabilistic systemic risk analysis of road networks, considering the spatial correlation of ground motion intensities, vulnerability of the network components, and the effect of interactions within the network, as well as, between roadway components and built environment to the network functionality. The system-level performance is examined through a global connectivity indicator, which depends on both physical damages to its components and induced functionality losses due to interactions with other systems. The proposed approach is applied to the road network in the city of Thessaloniki (Greece), to examine its applicability. In particular, the risk for such a road network is investigated, with a focus on the short-term impact of seismic hazards. Besides, the potential road blockages due to the collapse of adjacent buildings and overpass bridges are also considered, so as to identify possible criticalities associated with specific components/subsystems. The simulation outcome shows that the performance of the road network is highly influenced by the interdependencies. In other words, an unbiased functionality loss estimation can be delivered, only if a complex system-of-systems analysis is run. Furthermore, it is also found that building collapses indeed are the most likely cause of functionality losses of the road network, under seismic hazards.

Alipour and Shafei (2016) proposed a comprehensive framework on seismic resilience assessment of aging (highway) road networks. To estimate the damage probability of aging bridges during their service life, time-dependent fragility analysis was performed. To examine the influence of damageability of individual network components to the functionality of the whole system, the highway network across Los Angeles and Orange counties was selected as the test bed. An integrated traffic assignment model, taking into account the dynamic changes of capacity and demand after an earthquake event, was also used in that case study. The corresponding simulation result shows that extensive deterioration of the network components may result in a dramatic increase in the number of damaged bridges, leading to excessive indirect losses due to the downtime of highway networks.

Miller and Baker (2016) developed a framework linking travel accessibilities to the quantitative seismic risk assessment of road networks, so as to identify the corresponding communities at high risk for travel disruption after earthquake hazards. To that end, they have also proposed a practical activity-based traffic model, whereby the behavioural pattern of the travel of households will be characterized by their incomes. The case study on the road network across San Francisco Bay Area shows that the post-shock accessibility varies more strongly

as a function of travellers' geographic location, than as a function of their income class. Besides, the simulation outcome also reveals that those communities conducive to local trips by foot or bike could be less impacted by the accessibility losses.

Dong and Frangopol (2017) studied seismic resilience of the integrated system of healthcare-road network. In addition to the physical damage, the extra travel and waiting time were also employed as another societal measure. Based on their study, the seismic performance of the interdependent systems will be contingent upon both sub-systems. The corresponding case study demonstrates that bridge retrofit can be contributing remarkably to the improvement of seismic resilience of the integrated system, and the extra travel time of the injured can be reduced by up to 75%, owing to the retrofit.

Gehl and D'Ayala (2018) established an assessment model on functionality losses of road networks under the combined earthquake and flood hazards. In such a model, the multi-hazard interactions on the vulnerability level are considered by the functionality loss curves, obtained from the assembly of hazard-specific fragility curves for local damage mechanisms. On the hazard level, the potential overlap between earthquake and flood hazards is represented by a time window during which the effects of one hazard type on the infrastructure may still be in play. The developed modelling framework is implemented through a Bayesian Network, which enables the propagation of uncertainties and the computation of joint probabilities.

Gomez and Baker (2019) proposed an optimization framework on strategic decisions regarding whether to proactively retrofit or reactively repair bridges in road networks under seismic hazards, with the objective of minimizing the cost of maintaining a target network performance metric throughout a set of possible adverse scenarios. To that end, a two-stage stochastic programming approach is developed, which relates pre- and post-event decisions, accounting for the uncertainty throughout scenarios. Therefore, the optimization problem has been decomposed, and the analysis on large sets of scenarios is enabled.

Kilanitis and Sextos (2019) have proposed a holistic framework for the multi-criterion assessment and management of the functionality losses of Road Networks. Both the structural and monetary losses, along with the broader financial, connectivity and environmental impact of hazard levels with different annual rate of exceedance are put into context and employed as the comprehensive measure on the losses associated with earthquake-damaged Road Networks.

Li et al. (2019) studied the rockfall hazard and risk assessment on a (highway) road network across Jiuzhaigou area, in the wake of 2017 Ms 7.0 Jiuzhaigou earthquake, China. Through the combined analysis on the information of local rockfall occurrence and on the topographical setting, a 3D rockfall simulation has been enabled, so as to acquire the block count, velocity, flying height, and propagation probability. Estimation of the qualitative rockfall hazard and quantitative rockfall risk along the road network in the Jiuzhaigou area can therefore be generated. Such risk and hazard maps are useful, when it comes to different levels of decision-making for rockfall prevention and mitigation. In particular, it was also shown that dense forests can serve as a defensive measures against rockfalls, with regard to such a road network.

Feng et al. (2020) established an agent-based model, which enables the estimation on the cascading effect of earthquake-induced damage of road networks on the post-shock traffic sustained by those infrastructure networks. In such a model, in addition to the physical damage, the influence of the abrupt changes of the destination, and the potentially irrational behaviour of drivers on the traffic-carrying capacity of the road networks are also included and examined. From the case-study that they have carried out, it was found that, in cases of rush hours, the disorientation of large number of vehicles will substantially exacerbate the functionality losses of the earthquake-damaged road networks.

Kameshwar et al. (2020) developed a decision tree-based approach to determine potential traffic restriction and the corresponding duration, with regard to bridges of earthquake-damaged road networks. Specifically, three separate decision trees are developed to determine various traffic restrictions, pursuant to different levels

of damage to bridge components, including bridge closure, lane closure, and speed/load restriction. Corresponding to each of the three traffic restriction decision trees, another decision tree is also established to determine the duration of those restrictions. The proposed model was employed to examine the probabilistic seismic performance of a regional highway network in Memphis, Tennessee. The corresponding outcome shows that, compared to the conventional methods, the proposed model is able to yield a more nuanced and reasonable estimation on the post-shock functionality of that highway network.

Toma-Danila et al. (2020) proposed a new framework on the functionality loss estimation of large-scale road networks, under seismic hazards. In particular, such a framework employs GIS to define, geo-spatially analyse and represent road networks. To account for the large uncertainties, Monte Carlo simulations are run, with regard to the multiple scenario generation. The Dijkstra algorithm is used to analyse the connectivity loss, and its corresponding impact on the emergency intervention times and transit disruptions. To facilitate the customization, the framework has already been integrated in ArcGIS Desktop now, as a toolbox.

It is noteworthy to highlight that both the functionality and post-shock repair of modern Road Networks will be dependent upon a set of the other critical infrastructure systems. As an endeavour to shed light on the impact of those interdependences on the functionality losses of road networks in the post-shock stage, Zhao and Sun (2021) examined the seismic risk of the integrated Road Networks (RNs) and Electric Power Supply Systems (EPSSs). In particular, it shall be noted that, a dynamic, looped interdependence is assumed to be in play between those two networks, in their studies. Specifically, the repair of EPSSs is set to be contingent upon the functionality of the corresponding RN, in the sense that EPSS components can be repairable, only if accessible via the RN. In turn, the restoration of RN will also be influenced by the functionality of EPSS, as many restoration equipment of RN need the power to function. Accordingly, an agent-based model was then established, to deliver a nuanced modelling on the impact of that looped interdependence on the functionality losses of both the two physical networks. Based on the corresponding case-study, it was found that, regarding strong earthquakes, RNs can undergo a very significant, long-lasting functionality loss, if its repair is significantly contingent upon the functionality of EPSS, due to a downward spiral in play.

In the immediate aftermath of seismic hazards, it will be strategically crucial for road network to retain, at least, a fraction of its traffic-carrying capacity, to ensure the efficient evacuation of at-risk population to safe zones, and the timely dispatch of emergency response resources to the impacted area.

Lee et al. (2011) proposed a new non-sampling-based approach to assess the time-varying post-hazard flow capacity of road networks considering structural deterioration of their bridges. Such an approach evaluates the probability associated with different structural damage scenarios using the matrix-based system reliability method, and computes the corresponding flow capacities of road networks using a maximum flow capacity analysis algorithm. The matrix-based framework enables the integration of those results to obtain the probabilistic distributions and statistical moments of the flow capacity of road networks.

Chang et al. (2012) developed a methodology to find out the optimal bridge retrofit program, so as to maximize the post disaster traffic-carrying capacity of road networks. The uncertainties of the earthquake intensity, the physical damage and functionality of bridges are addressed by a Monte Carlo simulation framework with the established bridge fragility curves and damage-functionality relationships, and the effectiveness of preserving traffic-carrying capacity is calculated on the basis of a network design model. The proposed framework is applied on the road network in Memphis, Tennessee, and the corresponding outcome reveals that the proposed framework can find the solution efficiently, and thereby help the Operator maximize the utility of investment and minimize the functionality losses.

Table 2-12: Existing functionality loss models for road networks in the literature.

Reference	Methodology	Functions	Indicators	Critical components	Classification	Interdependencies of damage to other systems	Organisational issues
Sohn et al. (2003)	Risk analysis	Highway	Economic losses	Bridges	●	Not considered	Decision makers (to define the retrofit priority of bridges)
Kiremidjian et al. (2007)	Risk analysis and supply-demand analysis	Highway	Travel times	Bridges	●	Not considered	Not considered
Stergiou & Kiremidjian (2010)	Multi-dimensional loss analysis	Highway	Economic losses	Bridges	●	Not considered	Not considered
Lee et al. (2011)	Maximum flow capacity analysis	Highway	Network flow capacity	Bridges	●	Not considered	Not considered
Chang et al. (2012)	MC method and operational management	Highway	Budget-max. flow rate	Bridges	●	Not considered	Not considered
Pinto et al. (2012)	The object-oriented paradigm (OOP) for seismic hazard and the road network modelling..	Roadway network	Simple (SCL) and weighted (WCL) connectivity loss Moving average μ and moving standard deviation σ of SCL and WCL. Terminal reliability and mean annual frequency (MAF) of exceedance of SCL and WCL.	Trenches, embankments, slopes, bridges, tunnels	●	Not considered	Not considered
Argyroudis et al. (2015)	Probabilistic approach, MC simulations	Intercity road network	Connectivity loss	Bridges, road pavement (including liquefaction)	✓	Debris from collapsed buildings and bridges	Not considered
Alipour & Shafei (2016)	Origin-destination (O-D) analysis	Highway	Direct and indirect costs	Bridges	●	Not considered	Not considered
Miller & Baker (2016)	O-D analysis & ABM	Highway	Travel time	Bridges	●	Not considered	Not considered
Dong & Frangopol (2017)	Probabilistic functionality	Healthcare-bridge	Travel and waiting time	Bridges and hospitals	●	Healthcare networks	Coordinated rescue
Gehl & D'Ayala (2018)	Bayesian networks and multi-hazard analysis	Highway	Repair time & functionality loss	Bridges	✓	Not considered	Not considered
Gomez & Baker (2019)	Stochastic optimization	Highway	Travel time	Bridges	●	Not considered	Not considered
Kilanitis & Sextos (2019)	Seismic risk assessment and traffic analysis	Highway	Economic losses	Bridges	●	Not considered	Not considered
Li et al. (2019)	Rockfall modelling	Highway	Length of disrupted segment	Bridges and road segment	●	Not considered	Not considered

Reference	Methodology	Functions	Indicators	Critical components	Classification	Interdependencies of damage to other systems	Organisational issues
Feng et al. (2020)	Traffic flow modelling	City road network	Travel speed	Bridges	●	Not considered	Not considered
Kameshwar et al. (2020)	Decision tree	Highway	Travel time and distance	Bridges	●	Not considered	Not considered
Toma-Danila et al. (2020)	Seismic risk assessment and traffic analysis	City road network	Travel time	Bridges, road segments indirectly affected	✓	Debris from collapsed buildings, post-earthquake traffic pattern changes	Location of hospitals and fire stations
Zhao and Sun (2021)	Graph theory and ABM	Highway	Accessibility	Bridges	●	Power networks	Coordinated recovery

Classifications (concerning the applicability to RRE):

- ✓ Directly applicable
- Not directly applicable
- ✗ Not applicable

2.3.2.1.2 Railway networks

The scoping of systemic performance of railway networks compared with the highway networks is relatively less addressed in literature, yet, important remarks have been identified in the rail network functionality theme concerning seismicity. Ham et al. (2005) were among the pioneers introducing highway and rail networks as vulnerable systems to hazardous events, based on the influence of a hypothetical earthquake on New Madrid, US, and its direct/indirect impact on the surrounding regions. Through 5 scenarios, they demonstrate that even zones outside seismic risk can experience functionality losses due to the disruptions at a connecting region subject to hazard, and highway networks have interdependency with rail networks in terms of functionality losses following an earthquake.

Tatano & Tsuchiya (2008) presented the influence of Niigata-Chuetsu Earthquake on transportation disruption and associated effects through direct and indirect seismicity-induced losses in various regions of Japan. They formulate the spatial computable equilibrium model through multiple factors such as firm and household behavior, and look into equilibrium conditions before and after earthquakes to quantify earthquake impacts on the network. Miller-Hooks et al. (2012) constructed a framework to evaluate resilience of rail networks which has system-scale disruption potential under seismic events in the Western US. The paper also looks into optimal preparedness actions through a Monte Carlo simulation scheme given budgetary constraints. In this study, the authors quantitatively show the dependency of network resiliency level on different hazardous events as well as allocated budgets.

Identifying Hokkaido prefecture in Japan as a testbed, Du et al. (2015) proposed a probabilistic framework to handle transportation network vulnerability assessment with coexisting influences from network degradation and its seismic hazard exposure. They quantified the seismic vulnerability index based on conjunct existence of the difference of total generalized cost and component-wise probability of disruption. In their study, they look into sets of network links and identify the weak ones with and without consideration of degradation probabilities combined with freight volume.

Zu et al. (2020) proposed an empirical fragility approach to define train service disruption due to earthquakes and referred to the 1000-year earthquake catalogue for China for probabilistic seismic hazard analysis of the nationwide rail network. The authors evaluated the losses in train trips under different seismicity scenarios stemming from edge failures in the network and stressed that the majority of disruptions occur under non-damaging events but safety actions. Besides, they demonstrated that disruptions introduced due to seismicity is unevenly distributed throughout the regions and the disruption is not solely impacted by the magnitude and epicentre location, but a combination of network distribution and seismic demand.

Based on a complex network modelling approach, Yin & Wang (2020) developed network-scale vulnerability assessment of rail infrastructure in China to provide a basis for emergency management and rescue actions. In their study, they used existing train service data to express the operational characteristics reaching more than 3000 stations and 400 railway lines. They computed the degree statistics per node, identified top operating lines, performed betweenness analysis for multiple stations, and finally looked into clustering coefficients of the high-speed rails vs normal-speed ones. Due to hazard exposure, the authors determined the seismic impact in terms of trains affected and identified the critical stations in the network.

Looking at the overall trend in the railway network studies addressing seismicity-induced reduction in functionality, it is apparent that the structural aspects are usually not taken into consideration and the seismic exposure is performed more generically at the hazard level. This is due to the fact that the majority of the scope is attributed to the freight and passenger transportation analytics, leaving seismic performance of infrastructure outside the scope in general. It appears that integration of structure-specific seismic performance into network-scale analysis is not favoured due to complexity and rigorous modelling efforts, however, seems to be an essential direction for a better representation of seismic risk reflecting regionwide losses in rail transportation. Within TURNkey the system analysis of the railway network does not form part of the proposed work. Therefore none of the studies referred above is directly used in the test beds or within the TURNkey platform.

Table 2-13: Existing functionality loss models for railway networks in the literature.

Reference	Methodology	Functions	Indicators	Critical components	Classification	Interdependencies of damage to other systems	Organisational issues
Ham et al. (2005)	Interregional Commodity Flow Model	Highway and Rail Network	Least cost criterion, minimum distance travelled	Scenario-specific nodes on the transportation network	●	Not considered	Not considered
Tatano & Tsuchiya (2008)	Spatial Computable Equilibrium Model	Highway and Rail Network	Traffic volume of freight and passengers	Shinkansen (high-speed rail) and expressways	●	Not considered	Not considered
Miller-Hooks et al. (2012)	Two-Stage Stochastic Program	Rail Network	Time and cost	Generic capacity reduction and terminal failure	●	Not considered	Not considered
Du et al. (2015)	Seismic Vulnerability Index	Highway and Rail Network	Travel time and travel cost	Road embankments, bridges	●	Not considered	Not considered
Zhu et al. (2020)	Spatial Analysis and Complex Network Theory	Rail Network	Annual train trip losses	Physical damage and emergency shutdowns	●	Not considered	Not considered

Yin & Wang (2020)	Complex Network Model and Vulnerability Assessment	Rail Network	Trains affected	Roadbeds, tracks, and bridges as well as train speed	●	Not considered	Not considered
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Classifications (concerning the applicability to RRE):

- ✓ Directly applicable
- Not directly applicable
- ✗ Not applicable

2.3.2.1.3 Power networks

This section reviews the state-of-the-art on functionality losses of electric power networks, on the system level. Kameshwar et al. (2019) established a framework for the community-level management on the disaster resilience. Such a framework is inclusive and adaptive, as it enables stakeholders to examine different hazards and intensity measures, a variety of infrastructure systems, ex-ante and ex-post measures, infrastructure robustness and rapidity goals, as well as resources' availability. On the community level, disaster resilience is defined as the joint probability of all infrastructure systems being resilient. To assess these joint probabilities, the framework employs Bayesian networks, whose conditional probability tables are obtained through probabilistic damage and restoration simulations, i.e. the Monte Carlo Simulation. Based on the corresponding case study with regard to the transportation, water, and power infrastructure systems, as well as the built community in Seaside, Oregon, subjected to earthquake and tsunami, it was found that a very complicated interdependence among those three different networks is in play, and having a profound impact on the community resilience. Unrealistic resilience assessment outcome was found to be generated, for example, the water system recovers before the power network, if that interdependence has not been properly considered. Nozhati et al. (2019) proposed a sequential discrete optimization approach, as a decision-making framework of power networks. Mathematically, such an approach marries approximate dynamic programming and heuristics of recovery actions. Based on the case study associated with the power network across Gilroy, California, it was shown that such a developed methodology is able to identify near-optimal recovery decisions, and ultimately, sheds light on the gross functionality loss estimation of power networks, in the wake of damaging earthquakes. Sun et al. (2019) put forward an agent-based modelling (ABM) framework, to enable the nuanced examination on seismic resilience of modern power networks. Such an ABM was applied to gauge the resilience of a virtual, integrated system of power network and road network, subject to seismic hazards. Accordingly, *the Operators* of both the two networks are defined as the separate agents. The case study reveals that the societal loss of power networks could be increasing exponentially, alongside the seismic magnitude. Besides, with regard to strong earthquakes, the widespread damage of road networks will significantly hinder the restoration of power networks, which will substantially exacerbate their seismic loss, throughout the entirety of earthquake events.

Table 2-14: Existing functionality loss models for power networks in the literature.

Reference	Methodology	Functions	Indicators	Critical components	Interdependencies of damage to other systems	Organisational issues
Kameshwar et al. (2019)	Monte Carlo and Bayesian network	Power supply	Restoration time & functionality loss	Substations	Water networks, transportation networks, and buildings	Intertwined recovery

Nozhati et al. (2019)	Dynamic programming	Power supply	Number of people affected	Substations	Not considered	Not considered
Sun et al. (2019b)	ABM	Power supply	Number of people affected	Substations	Not considered	Not considered

2.3.2.2 Port facilities

Ports represent a multicomponent system in which each element has its own feature and vulnerability. Under earthquake loading, various port facilities can be damaged - from wharves with their supporting systems to cranes and other utilities. Potential disruptions of one element caused by a seismic event may trigger a domino effect that influences the performance of the entire system. Assessments of seaport seismic risk rarely address interdependency problems, also referred to in the literature as cascade or domino effects.

This Section presents a literature review of the studies on the assessment of functionality loss of earthquake-damaged ports.

Pachakis & Kiremidjian (2004) carried out a study to calculate operational losses occurring after scenario earthquakes in multi-terminal container ports. A queuing model with a maximum wait capacity is implemented for incoming container ships. Expected cargo throughput (based on all possible damage states) is calculated for the port in both the damaged and undamaged state and then compared.

The study carried out by Werner & Taylor (2004) evaluates the systemwide seismic performance and upgrade options of several berths in the Port of Oakland. A simplified operational model is used to evaluate business interruption losses by comparing the average daily demands to the average daily post-earthquake capacities.

Na & Shinozuka (2009) developed a simulation-based framework to estimate losses in ports containing quay walls. The study calculates damage using specifically developed fragility curves for quay wall damage and then input that information into a terminal operation program to calculate resulting throughput. Total loss is estimated through the use of fragility curves calculated from resulting throughputs. This study also features a retrofit to the quay wall and calculates system fragility curves for both conditions.

A first attempt to address the interdependencies among the elements of a port system under seismic loading was performed by Kakderi et al. (2013) with reference to the port of Thessaloniki (Greece) in the framework of the European SYNER-G project. The methods and tools developed in SYNER-G were applied and validated in Thessaloniki's port. The Performance Indicator (PI) was calculated based on the estimated damage and functionality losses of the different components. Port performance loss can be attributed either to damage occurred to waterfronts and/or cranes, or malfunction of cranes due to loss of electric power supply.

Burden et al. (2016) developed a risk framework for forecasting earthquake-induced losses in port systems. The framework used to calculate port losses is based on the use of spatially correlated ground motion intensity measures that estimate damage to pile-supported wharves and container cranes, the repair costs and downtimes subsequently determined via repair models for both types of structures, and the impact on cargo handling operations calculated via logistical models of the port system. Results are expressed in the form of loss exceedance curves.

Recently, a simulation-based methodology for the assessment of the seismic risk of ports as systems of interconnected structural and infrastructural elements is developed and applied to a large commercial port in Italy by Conca et al. (2020). The results of the analyses are expressed as the loss of performance of an element

that can be attributed to either direct damage or interdependencies (i.e., domino effects). The case study is the port of Gioia Tauro, which is one of the selected testbeds in TURNkey project (i.e. the TB5). Therefore, such approach is briefly illustrated in Section 3 with reference to TB5.

Table 2-15: Studies available in the literature on the estimation of seismic functional and systemic losses for ports.

Reference	Methodology	Functions	Indicators	Critical components	Classification	Interdependencies	Organisational issues
Pachakis & Kiremidjian (2004)	Operational losses occurring after scenario earthquakes in multi-terminal container ports based on a simulation	Port system	Cargo throughput	Wharves and cranes	×	Not considered	Decision makers
Werner & Taylor (2004)	Operational model to evaluate seismic performance of several berths in the Port of Oakland and to assess business interruption losses by comparing the	Port waterfront	Cargo throughput	Wharves	×	Not considered	Decision makers
Na & Shinozuka (2009)	Simulation-based study to estimate losses in ports (containing quay walls) based on purposely developed fragility curves for quay wall damage and a	Port waterfront	Cargo throughput	Wharves (i.e. quay walls)	×	Not considered	Decision makers
Kakderi et al. (2012; 2013)	First attempt to address interdependencies among the elements of the port of Thessaloniki (Greece).	Port system	Performance indicator (PI) of the port (i.e. container	Wharves, cranes, electric power supply	●	Interdependencies among port critical components	Decision makers
Burden et al. (2016)	Risk framework for forecasting earthquake losses in port systems. It looks at the port as a system and allows for the evaluation of performance based on	Port system	Cargo throughput	Wharves; cargo handling components; terminals, including the	●	Interdependencies among port critical components	Decision makers (i.e. port stakeholders)
Conca et al. (2020)	Simulation-based methodology for the assessment of seismic risk of port systems by addressing interdependencies among port components (i.e., domino effects) and application to the	Port system	Performance indicator (PI) of the port (in terms of container throughput)	Wharves; cargo handling components; elements of the electric power system; terminals,	✓	Interdependencies among port critical components	Decision makers (i.e. Port Authority, Italian Department of Civil Protection)

Explanation:

Classifications (concerning the applicability to RRE):

- ✓ Directly applicable
- Not directly applicable
- × Not applicable

3 FUNCTIONALITY LOSS MODELS IN THE TURNKEY TESTBEDS

3.1 TB-1: Bucharest, Romania [INFP]

3.1.1 Description of the Road Network in Bucharest

Bucharest is one of Europe's most endangered capitals due to earthquakes (Toma-Danila and Armas, 2017; Pavel and Vacareanu, 2016). The city was previously affected by strong earthquakes in the Vrancea seismic area (such as the ones on 10 November 1940, Mw=7.7, at 150 km depth, and on 4 March 1977, Mw=7.4, at 94 km depth) and its level of exposure and vulnerability is significantly higher nowadays (Pavel and Vacareanu, 2016) – both considering the conditions of the built environment but the critical infrastructure, the traffic problem and overall low resilience levels. The city faces regular traffic jams, being ranked as Europe's number one capital (5th in the world in 2017, 11th in 2018) when it comes to the typical congestion level (TomTom, 2021). Beside traffic, Bucharest's road network maintenance and serviceability status are precarious, with much dysfunction related to the quality of embankments, bridges, or over- or underpasses; poor construction and maintenance; and limitations in the full utilization of roads' size due to illegal (and unsanctioned) parking in many cases or constantly exceeded deadlines for repair or new roadwork (Toma-Danila et al., 2020).

Figure 3-1 Bucharest Road Network, according to OSM data (at the level of September 2016). Updated vector free data can be retrieved from sources such as the Geofabrik GIS Data Portal (<http://download.geofabrik.de>).

For describing the entire Bucharest Road Network, OpenStreetMap (OSM) vectoral road network data is considered to be suitable for research (Toma-Danila et al., 2020), considering that the municipality doesn't yet provide its own curated GIS data. In an analysis aimed at evaluating travel times of emergency intervention vehicles, the possibility for them to legally use the specially delimited tramway lines, which creates a separate

and almost always free access route in important areas of the city, such as the inner belt, is important to account for. The attributes of OSM data consist of hierarchy class (importance of the road segment), name, one-way restrictions, maximum speed allowed, layer profile (Z elevation), classification as bridge or tunnel. Traffic data for Bucharest can be downloaded from various services such as TomTom Traffic Stats, available at <https://support.move.tomtom.com/products/traffic-stats/>. All of this are highly important in modelling the traffic flow across the network – given that the network is defined in a way in which connectivity is ensured.

3.1.2 Loss estimation models selected for the Road Network in Bucharest

3.1.2.1 Functionality loss models at component level

3.1.2.1.1 For the bridges

Mean fragility functions from Crowley et al.(2011), for the corresponding structural typology (mostly reinforced concrete) can be used to compute the damage probability (which was found to be for complete collapse quite small – less than 2% for worst-case earthquake scenarios, according to Toma-Danila et al., 2020). A functionality loss model similar to the one proposed for TB2 can be also applied to TB1 (Table 3-1), but further analysis of local repairing capabilities is needed. However, for immediate aftermath analysis (dedicated also to rapid response evaluation) – 100% loss of functionality when the last two damage states are encountered (complete and major damage in Crowley et al., 2011) can provide a good estimation.

3.1.2.1.2 For the roads blocked by building debris

In Toma-Danila et al. (2020), the equation in Moroux et al. (2004) was used to determine the extent of debris generated by collapsed buildings and could also be used in this study. Also, the equation of Argyroudis (2010) further described for TB2 is a more advanced potential option – but consideration regarding the data available for affected buildings need to be made. If using building-by-building data, information from sources such as the official registry of buildings evaluated in seismic risk classes or urgency categories (PMB: <https://amccrs-pmb.ro/liste-imobile>, geo-referenced by RE:RISE: <https://kepler.gl/demo/map?mapUrl=https://dl.dropboxusercontent.com/s/fbdddwwfw5y7plj/Digitalizare%20AMCCRS.json>) – covering however only 1% of the total residential building stock in Bucharest (2762 buildings), could have enough attributes enabling a good evaluation of road blockage probability. Even so, for this data source, links with fragility functions or other assumptions needing to be assigned to evaluate the damage state for other earthquakes than the control earthquakes used for placing them in seismic risk classes. If using results from generic loss estimation at census tract or sector level, identification of prone to blockage areas is much difficult.

$$\text{Affected area (m)} = 2/3 * \text{Number of storeys} \quad (3-1)$$

3.1.2.1.3 Traffic pattern changes

Following an earthquake, traffic patterns within a major city significantly change, depending also on the time of the earthquake (and its associated traffic). This can be related to multiple causes, such as the people desire to ensure that their relatives or assets are safe, people evacuating affected areas or entering in them with no knowledge of the lack of connectivity, people in need to reach their jobs as responsible in emergency situations etc. In many cases, post-earthquake traffic is characterized by the violation of traffic rules. The chaos in and

around the hospitals could be a significant problem (as was during the 1977 Vrancea earthquake, in case of Floreasca Hospital in Bucharest).

For estimating post-event traffic patterns, a simplified approach can be used (Toma-Danila et al., 2020), based on the following traffic modification parameters:

- for areas closer to 100 m (calculated on roads as service area not as buffer) to affected road segments: 2 km h^{-1} ,
- for areas closer to 500 m: 5 km h^{-1} .

3.1.2.2 Loss estimation models at system level

3.1.2.2.1 Connectivity loss

Connectivity loss can be assessed both individually – for an origin-destination (O-D) pair – and also globally (Poljansek et al., 2012), depending on the purpose of the analysis. Given that for TB1 the aim is mainly to evaluate if hospitals or fire stations are still connected after an earthquake with areas in need of emergency intervention, connectivity can be evaluated for O-D pairs; given that in most cases areas in need of emergency intervention are the ones not accessible easily (due to traffic and debris), an adjacency index could be calculated, referring to which is the closest accessible road network segment to the destination and which is the remaining distance to destination. Road network analysis modules (such as ArcGIS, used in Toma-Danila et al., 2020) can determine, based on service area analysis, polygons not anymore connected to the rest of the network – including also road segment not directly affected, but inaccessible due to other segments' blockage.

3.1.2.2.2 Travel duration

By using the Dijkstra algorithm (or others such as the A* algorithm, Johnson's algorithm or the Floyd–Warshall algorithm), travel duration can be determined both for O-D pairs and for serviceability areas around facilities (service area analysis). For Bucharest, an example of service areas computed using Dijkstra algorithm through ArcGIS with network analyst can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 3-2 Service areas for fire stations, (a) pre-earthquake and (b) post-earthquake, considering the worst-case model, for the typical traffic scenario on Monday at 08:00 LT (Toma-Danila et al., 2020).

3.1.2.2.3 Hospital treatment capabilities

In order to mitigate the risks but also manage the intervention properly, a good understanding of post-earthquake rapid response resources, beside safe access routes, is needed. This will need to account, in a time-dependent way, for the:

- Available treatment facilities and considerations regarding suitable equipment for specific interventions (in correspondence with typical earthquake wounds such as fractures or burns) and surgery rooms, number of ambulances available and types (number of stretchers, with or without specialized physicians in emergency situations etc.), but also personnel and their potential reach-to-facility time.
- Structural and non-structural hospital damage.
- in COVID-19 times medical care raises new issues: some hospitals are devoted to the treatment of coronavirus patients only, the impact of hospital availability for a certain type of patient with specific injury and disease conditions needing to be accounted for in practice and in vulnerability analysis.

For Bucharest, we are in the process of defining a loss of functionality model considering all these aspects in a multi-criteria decision analysis framework and rating system (using also the work of World Health Organization & Pan American Health, 2015), time-dependent and in relation with potential number of patients with different wounds and different ground motion parameters, but as data is still sparse and some aspects are limited or confidential, results are still pending.

3.2 TB-2: Pyrenees Mountain Range, France [BRGM, UCL]

Figure 3-3: Focus areas within TB-2

TB-2 in the Pyrenees mountain range in France involves two specific area, as shown in Figure 3-3:

- The 44 km high-speed railway line between Perpignan (France) and Figueras (Spain) operated by LFP Perthus;
- The Luchon Valley consisting of the road network system (RDN) connecting 53 municipalities, as detailed in Figure 3-4.

In the following, we describe in details the RDN in Luchon Valley, and the corresponding assumptions considered to study the functionality losses at both the component and the systemic levels.

3.2.1 Description of the Road Network in Luchon Valley

Luchon Valley has 9195 inhabitants (INSEE, 2017), where 30% of the population is concentrated in the municipality of Bagneres-de-Luchon (BL) with 2570 habitants. The RDN in Luchon Valley consists of 689 edges connected by 607 nodes (571 road segments and 118 bridges). The RDN dataset is collected from national databases of infrastructure (BD_CARTO and BD_TOPO). The treatment and clean-up of the original dataset results in the creation of two GIS shapefiles (RDN_NODES and RDN_EDGES), which fully describe the network topology (see Figure 3-5 and Figure 3-6).

Figure 3-4: The original RDN in Luchon Valley

ID		LAT	LON
1	1	42,865082119620176	0,750081638064562
2	2	42,864924187073932	0,749843171134209
3	3	42,915854974746679	0,691905928164630
4	4	42,915448895053487	0,691848640790853
5	5	42,866176479534019	0,749073100675110
6	6	42,974060957218803	0,646912098167682
7	7	42,972774154091816	0,646903072083811
8	8	42,891871046514282	0,703271794068461
9	9	42,883925484980672	0,714778041299269
10	10	42,985473412344540	0,636423949148825

Figure 3-5: Extract from the attribute table of RDN_NODES shapefile

	TYPE	START	END
1	bridge	36	500
2	road segment	501	502
3	bridge	379	504
4	road segment	505	31
5	bridge	502	503
6	road segment	504	119
7	bridge	506	261
8	road segment	507	508
9	bridge	453	505
10	road segment	506	231

Figure 3-6: Extract from the attribute table of RDN_EDGES shapefile

The layout of the studied RDN is detailed in Figure 3-4. In RDN_EDGES, the *START* and *END* fields represent the ID numbers of the nodes from RDN_NODES shapefile, from which it is possible to assemble the

topological graph of the network, along with its adjacency matrix (which may be used in subsequent connectivity analyses). Other RDN features may be specified, depending on the level of network analysis that is pursued (e.g., travel speed along roads, hierarchy of roads, etc.). The data illustrated in Figure 3-5 and Figure 3-6 constitute the strict minimum of RDN features that are required in order to perform connectivity analyses (i.e., whether two points in the network are connected or not).

It is assumed here that the RDN under study consists of two vulnerable types of components (see Table 5-1 and Table 5-2 in Appendix I):

- The bridges in Luchon Valley that are subject to direct damage due to earthquakes and thus might become inaccessible and not functional. Bridges are identified in the RDN_EDGES shapefile by the value 'bridge' in the *TYPE* field. Their characteristics (structural features, topology) are described more in detail in Table 3.5 of deliverable report D4.2 (Faravelli et al., 2021).
- The roads nearby the buildings in BL that might be blocked because of the debris resulting from the collapsed buildings. The vulnerable roads in BL are manually identified: we select the road segments in BL that are subject to blockage due to presence buildings directly along the roadside. Then, we count the number of buildings to be associated to each of the vulnerable road segments using Google Maps. Figure 3-7 shows the spatial extent of the roads subject to the blockage from building debris in BL. We classify such roads in the RDN_EDGES shapefile by the value 'debris' in the *TYPE* field.

Other edges that do not enter into any of the above two categories ('bridge' and 'debris') are identified in the RDN_EDGES shapefile by the value 'road segment' in the *TYPE* field: they are assumed to always remain accessible and functional (i.e., non-vulnerable components). More in-depth studies could also include other types of vulnerable components, such as edges exposed of induced ground failure (e.g., landslides, rockfalls): whatever the type of vulnerability components considered, the main principles of functional loss analysis remain the same.

Figure 3-7: Zoom of the BL area, where road segments potentially blocked by building debris are identified

3.2.2 Loss estimation models selected for the Road Network in Luchon Valley

In order to study the functionality losses for the RDN in Luchon Valley, we define functionality metrics and indicators at both the component and system levels.

3.2.2.1 Functionality loss models at component level

3.2.2.1.1 For the bridges

The RDN across Luchon comprises 118 bridges, of which 89 beam-type bridges, 1 truss bridge and 28 arch bridges. The fragility functions of the bridges describe in Table 3.5 of deliverable report D4.2 (Faravelli et al., 2021) are used here. From the four physical damage states used for bridges (DS0: Intact, DS1: Minor Damage, DS2: Moderate Damage, DS3: Major Damage), the functionality models are defined in Table 3-1. It is based on literature reviews and direct surveys of road network operators (Gehl, 2017; Gehl & D'Ayala, 2018; Shinozuka et al., 2003).

Table 3-1: Proposed functionality models for bridges. FLA stands for functional losses at the end of the absorption phase, and FLR for functional losses during the recovery phase.

Damage state	Disruption duration (days)	Accessibility	FLA	FLR
DS0	-	Yes	-	-
DS1	1-90	Yes	25-50% speed	0-10% speed
DS2	60-120	No	100% lane closure	50% lane closure
DS3	90-150	No	100% lane closure	100% lane closure

The proposed functionality loss metrics at the bridge level are useful to assess the performance of the network in the immediate aftermath of the earthquake (FLA), but also to estimate recovery times and time-dependent performance indicators (disruption duration, FLR).

3.2.2.1.2 For the roads blocked by building debris

In order to quantify the probability that a given road segment is blocked by debris from collapsed buildings, the first step consists in estimating the number of collapsed buildings along the road. The built area of $N = 1787$ residential buildings in BL is represented as a polygon of homogeneous seismic vulnerability (vulnerability index $V = 0.7$), as defined in D4.2 (Faravelli et al., 2003). Then, the distribution of damage states is obtained by applying the semi-empirical vulnerability method by Lagomarsino & Giovinazzi (2006): the mean damage grade μ_D is expressed as a function of the macroseismic intensity MMI (which is obtained from the distribution of the intensity measure IM via ground-motion intensity conversion equations):

$$\mu_D = 2.5 \left[1 + \tanh \left(\frac{MMI + 6.25V - 13.1}{2.3} \right) \right] \quad (3-2)$$

Ultimately, the distribution of damage states in BL, based on the EMS-98 damage scale (Grünthal, 1998), is obtained by applying a discrete beta distribution based on the value of μ_D (Lagomarsino & Giovinazzi, 2006). For the current objective, only N_{D5} , the number of buildings in damage state D5 (Collapse), is of interest: the number of buildings N_r along a given road segment, as identified in Figure 3-7, is then used to approximate

the number of collapsed buildings $N_{r,D5}$ that have the potential to block the road (assuming a homogeneous distribution of damages across the whole built area):

$$N_{r,D5} = \frac{N_r}{N} N_{D5} \quad (3-3)$$

Given a collapsed building, several models for the estimation of the spatial extent of debris have been proposed in the literature (Argyroudis, 2010), depending on the collapse mode of the building. The collapse model B from Argyroudis (2010) corresponds to a collapse in one direction (which is the case of most adjacent buildings in city centres), as shown in Figure 3-8.

Figure 3-8: Collapse model B from Argyroudis (2010)

This collapse model evaluates the debris width W_d as follows:

$$W_d = \sqrt{W^2 + \frac{2 \cdot k_y \cdot W \cdot Y}{\tan c}} - W \quad (3-4)$$

with the parameters W (building width), Y (building height), k_y (ratio of collapsed volume vs initial building volume) and c (angle of the inclination of collapse). A survey of the population of buildings in the BL built area has led to the identification of average building dimensions: $W = 15$ m and $Y = 12$ m (around 3 stories). The parameters k_y and c are assumed to follow a normal distribution, according to Argyroudis et al. (2015): $E[k_y] = 0.5$, $\text{CoV}(k_y) = 30\%$, $E[c] = 45^\circ$, $\text{CoV}(c) = 30\%$; where $E[.]$ and $\text{CoV}(.)$ respectively represent the mean value and coefficient of variation of a given variable.

With the above assumptions, uncertain parameters may be sampled in order to generate a distribution of the debris width W_d (see Figure 3-9).

Argyroudis et al. (2015) propose the following functionality loss model, based on the valued of W_d :

- FL0: when $W_d \leq W_{br}$; the road segment is “open”;
- FL1: when $W_{br} < W_d \leq W_{br} + W_r - 3.5$; the road segment is only “open for emergency”;
- FL2: when $W_d > W_{br} + W_r - 3.5$; the road segment is “closed”.

In the above functionality loss model, W_r represents the width of the road, and W_{br} the distance between the building and the road side. The distance of 3.5m plays a role in the model because it roughly represents the width of an emergency car or truck.

Figure 3-9: Cumulative distribution function of W_d , obtained from the sampling of uncertain parameters

Finally, the probability Pr_i that a given road segment reaches a functionality loss level FL_i is approximated by the following expression, as proposed by Argyroudis et al. (2015):

$$Pr_i = 1 - [1 - P(FL_i)]^{N_r, D5} \quad (3-5)$$

where $P(FL_i)$ is obtained by checking the probability that W_d corresponds the FL_i criteria.

The above expression is obtained by aggregating the blockage probabilities $P(FL_i)$ (for a single building) over the total length of the road segment: because only one blockage due to one collapsed building is enough to block the road segment, the failure event of the road segment may be seen an in-series system, where each collapsed building has the potential to block the road (i.e., the survival event of the edge is decomposed into a series system of individual survivals to each building collapse). This formulation represents the upper bound of the actual blockage probability of the whole road segment, since it is based on assumption that all blockage events from single buildings are independent from each other. This assumption is used here, since it guarantees more conservative outcomes.

3.2.2.2 Loss estimation models at system level

3.2.2.2.1 Connectivity loss

Connectivity analysis is the most straightforward system loss measure: it is expressed as a binary variable that measures whether it is possible to establish a connected route between two points A and B of the network. The connectivity is assessed by building the adjacency matrix from the graph of the network (i.e., *START* and *END* fields of the RDN_EDGES shapefile). Depending on the functional loss of components after the event, the adjacency matrix is updated (removal of non-accessible edges) in order to compute the connectivity loss in the absorption phase.

The global connectivity performance of the system is assumed to be represented by the simple connectivity loss (SCL) (Poljansek et al., 2012), which represents the ratio of the remaining number of connected origin points after the event over the initial number of connected origins, averaged over the destinations:

$$SCL = 1 - \left\langle \frac{N_e^i}{N_o^i} \right\rangle_i \quad (3-6)$$

where N_e^i is the number of origin points connected to destination i after the earthquake, and N_o^i is the number of origin points connected to destination i under normal conditions. The ratio is averaged over all destination points. This measure is useful to quantify the global connectivity overall the whole network, however it may be sometimes preferable to focus on specific origin-destination couples: this is especially the case in the immediate aftermath of the earthquake (rapid response phase), where specific operational needs come into play (e.g., accessibility between damaged areas and rescue centres).

3.2.2.2.2 Travel duration

By accounting for the length of edges, and the corresponding speed limits (or usual travel times along each edge), it is also possible to estimate the travel duration between two points A and B of the network. It is assessed by adding weights in the adjacency matrix and by looking for the shortest/quickest path, using for instance Dijkstra's algorithm. This loss measure brings more information than connectivity analysis, since it is able to detect performance loss even though origins and destinations are still connected: due to inaccessible edges, a detour between A and B might be needed, resulting in a longer travel duration.

This loss measure has been formalized by Gehl et al. (2017), who propose the following expression for R_{TT} (increase of travel time):

$$R_{TT} = 1 - \frac{TT_0}{TT} \quad (3-7)$$

where TT and TT_0 are the travel times under damaged and normal conditions (for a given origin-destination couple), respectively. In the case of interruption of all possible paths between the two TAZs, TT is set to infinity (i.e. $R_{TT} = 1$, equivalent to connectivity loss).

Such computations may be done by accounting for traffic flows and traffic congestion, in order to provide more realistic results. However, such an approach requires specific data (origin-destination matrices, which should be dynamic in order to reflect the evolution of traffic after the earthquake) and robust traffic models. Given the timeframe of the absorption phase and the urgency to provide emergency responders with rapid situational awareness, models accounting for traffic congestions would be too long to implement. Therefore, the above loss measures are estimated by assuming free-flow conditions.

3.2.2.2.3 Recovery time

As another aspect of the seismic risk assessment, repair time also plays a crucial role to the loss estimation of earthquake-damaged road networks. In the meantime, it is self-evident that post-shock repair of road networks is rather dynamic and stochastic. Therefore, in such a Deliverable, an agent-based model is proposed as an adaptive approach to track the post-shock repair trajectory of road networks. Specifically, the *Repair Unit*, who runs the post-shock repair is assumed as the *Agent*, whose behavioural pattern is shaped by a set of behavioural attributes. In such a particular case study, given the level of importance of the roads analysed and their location, only one agent is used.

In each realization of the simulations, as a strategy to quicken the restoration of the traffic-carrying capacity of the global network, those damaged bridges will be ranked based on their betweenness centrality. Mathematically, the betweenness centrality of bridge v is computed according to equation $g(v) = \sum_{s \neq v \neq t} \frac{\sigma_{st}(v)}{\sigma_{st}}$ (3-8):

$$g(v) = \sum_{s \neq v \neq t} \frac{\sigma_{st}(v)}{\sigma_{st}} \quad (3-8)$$

where σ_{st} is the total number of shortest paths from node s to node t , $\sigma_{st}(v)$ is the number of those paths that pass through v (Brandes 2001). A ranked repair list can therefore be generated, based on such a criterion, following the seismic hazard. The *agent* is then set to depart from the *Repair Centre* and start to repair the first bridge (namely, the one with the largest value of betweenness centrality) on that list. As an endeavour to make the simulation tractable, in this Deliverable, the repair time for each bridge with will be determined by the two behavioural attributes of the agent, namely, V_b and E_b , which refer to the traveling speed of the *agent*, and its repair efficiency, respectively. Hence, for each individual bridge j (the number of which will be denoted as N), the time needed to start and finish its repair will then be determined following equations:

$$T_1 = T_0 + SD_0/V_b \quad 3-9$$

$$R_j = T_j + F_{L,j}/E_b, \quad j = 1: N \quad 3-10$$

$$T_j = R_{j-1} + SD_j/V_b, \quad j = 2: N \quad 3-11$$

3.2.2.3 Example of loss estimation for the Road Network in Luchon Valley

This sub-section provides an example of rapid loss estimation for the RDN of Luchon Valley (TB-2): instead of conventional Monte-Carlo simulations (i.e., sampling of ground shaking field, sampling of bridge damage states, sampling of functional losses, etc.), a Bayesian updating framework is adopted in order to account to observations gathered from the field (e.g., recordings from nearby seismic stations, observations that some bridges have failed). The details of the Bayesian procedure are extensively explained in the upcoming deliverable report D4.8 of Task 4.5.

The proposed Bayesian model currently relies on the estimation of the connectivity loss of the network, i.e. whether two given locations along the network are still connected or not (binary indicator). Since the analysis is limited to simple connectivity, it is proposed to reduce the complexity of the problem by building a conceptual network (i.e., *Super-Network*) based on the physical one, via the following steps (see Figure 3-10):

- a) Starting from a physical network with n nodes and m edges (among which, q bridges represent vulnerable edges), only nodes that have a degree equal to 1 (extremities of the network) or strictly above 2 (intersections) are kept as nodes of interest.
- b) By virtually removing the q vulnerable edges from the adjacency matrix of the network, it is possible to quickly identify all nodes that are accessible from each other without crossing a bridge (i.e., the nodes that stay connected with each other in the altered adjacency matrix).
- c) These nodes are grouped into a *Super-Node*: by definition, all nodes belonging to the same *Super-Node* are always connected with each other. If a bridge is used to connect two nodes within the

same *Super-Node*, it may be removed from the network (such as bridge #4 in Figure 3-10). This assumption is only valid when performing a simple connectivity analysis since other performance measures based on travel distance or duration would require the knowledge of alternate paths and so on.

d) The sets of bridges (i.e. vulnerable paths) that are linking two *Super-Nodes* are identified: this step is facilitated by the fact that only nodes of degree 2 may constitute vulnerable paths (i.e., extremities and intersections are absorbed in *Super-Nodes*). These paths are referred to as *Super-Edges*, and they represent sub-systems of bridges in series. Bridges may be then represented by the coordinates of their centroids.

Figure 3-10: Illustration of the construction of a Super-Network from a physical network.

As a result, the *Super-Network* (Figure 3-11) and is composed of:

- 59 *Super-Nodes* out of 607 nodes;
- 191 *Super-Edges* out of 689 edges;
- 111 *Super-Components*, where we define the *Super-Components* as the vulnerable infrastructure components under study linking the *Super-Nodes*: 99 bridges and 12 vulnerable roads susceptible to building debris blockage.

Figure 3-11: Left: Physical RDN of Luchon Valley; Right: Conceptual Super-Network for connectivity analysis

This structure is implemented in the corresponding Bayesian Network (BN). The updating capabilities of the BN are tested with a hypothetical M_w 5.4 earthquake scenario, located 0.50° lon and 42.833° lat (see Figure 3-12). Hypothetical observations from 7 seismic stations and damage measures on 5 bridges are set as evidence in the BN (3 survivals and 2 failures).

The output of the simulation is shown in Figure 3-12 and Figure 3-13. The Bayesian updating is especially useful for reducing the uncertainties in the estimated distribution of losses, and for detecting the fastest or safest routes, depending on the origin and destination points investigated.

Figure 3-12: Situation map of Luchon Valley case study area

- Probability of accessibility between BL and rescue centre: 0.97011
- Average travel distance between BL and rescue centre: 54.6611 km
- Shortest route between BL and rescue centre: via 10002 (MLS #11), 52.52 km with 0.11322 probability of accessibility
- Safest route between BL and rescue centre: via 10041 (MLS #753), 59.78 km with 0.84611 probability of accessibility

Figure 3-13: The output of the functionality loss model for the RDN in Luchon Valley

3.3 TB-3: Hveragerði, South Iceland and Húsavík, North Iceland [UIce]

The towns of TB-3 are located in the two fracture zones of the country, Hveragerði in the South Iceland Seismic Zone (SISZ) and Húsavík in the Tjörnes Fracture Zone (TFZ) in the North. Since the commencement of regional monitoring of weak- and strong-motion in the zones started in the late 80's and early 90's, no strong earthquakes have occurred in the TFZ, whereas four strong earthquakes have occurred in the SISZ. These are the Mw6.0 Vatnafjöll earthquake on 25 May 1987, the Mw6.4 Holt earthquake on 17 June and Mw6.5 Hestfjall earthquake on 21 June 2000, and the 29 May 2008 Mw6.3 Ölfus earthquake. The Vatnafjöll earthquake occurred in the Eastern end of the SISZ, and the others occurred progressively further to the west, with the Ölfus earthquake occurring in the Western end of the SISZ. These earthquakes have been the subject of a large number of geophysical and seismological studies (Einarsson 2014).

In particular, many studies on the corresponding earthquake strong-motions have been carried out (Sigbjörnsson and Ólafsson 2004; Halldórsson et al. 2007; Sigbjörnsson et al. 2007, 2009; Rupakhety and Sigbjörnsson 2009; Halldórsson and Sigbjörnsson 2009; Rupakhety et al. 2010; Rahpeyma et al. 2019; Kowsari et al. 2020; Sonnemann et al. 2020; Darzi et al. 2021b). While some describe partially the earthquake effects, other studies have focused on characterizing the vulnerability of the exposed building stock, primarily due to the June 2000 and May 2008 earthquakes (Bessason et al. 2012, 2014, 2020; Bessason and Bjarnason 2016; Darzi et al. 2021a), non-structural elements (Thorvaldsdóttir et al. 2020), and on the societal and psychological effects (Akason et al. 2006a, b; Bödvarsdóttir et al. 2006; Thordardóttir et al. 2018a, b). The impact on exposed infrastructures from those earthquakes followed the same pattern, as the population of the region, which increases from East to West, with the Eastern part being very rural, and the Western part having several towns within the microseismic area. In particular, the Ölfus earthquake occurred in between four towns of which over approx. 12 thousand people were located in the near-fault region.

There is very limited research at present on functionality loss modelling for exposed buildings and infrastructure in the transform zones in Iceland. The most recent but narrow efforts relate to buried wastewater systems in Hveragerði (Sigfúsdóttir 2020). However, a holistic approach to seismic risk assessment using system dynamics methodology (Thorvaldsdóttir and Sigbjörnsson 2014; Þorvaldsdóttir 2016) is currently being carried out where the recovery processes of the towns of Selfoss and Hveragerði are being modelled. This is done within the context of the TURNkey project, WP5, Task 5.2. In this approach the behaviour and dynamics of complex systems over time, in this case the recovery timeline of a municipality in the SISZ due to a damaging earthquake, will be modelled to estimate how long it takes to repair all buildings and the associated temporary housing cost. The output of this study is expected to highlight the infrastructure and/or processes that are important for a future functionality loss model development.

3.4 TB-4: Patras and Aegio, Greece [NOA]

3.5 TB-5: Maritime Port in Gioia Tauro, Italy [EUC]

3.5.1 Brief description of the seaport of Gioia Tauro

A port is a complex system composed of interconnected structures and infrastructures, that constitute a framework supporting the functionality of the entire multi-component system. Under earthquake loading, different port facilities can be damaged: from wharves with their supporting systems to cranes and other utilities. A potential disruption of one port element may trigger a domino (or cascade) effect that influences the performance of the entire system.

Within the port of Gioia Tauro, a variety of facilities exists, such as different typologies of wharf structures, infrastructure for cargo handling and storage, utility systems (e.g. electric power system), etc. Figure 3-14 shows an overview of the port of Gioia Tauro and Figure 3-15 shows a picture of a few infrastructure components of the Gioia Tauro port.

Figure 3-14: Overview of the port system of Gioia Tauro.

Figure 3-15: Picture of a few infrastructure components located within the Gioia Tauro port area.

3.5.2 Functionality loss estimation model adopted for the port system of Gioia Tauro

A simulation-based methodology was developed at EUCENTRE to assess the seismic response of a seaport system by addressing interdependencies among port elements. Indeed, the port system of Gioia Tauro is modelled as a system composed of a certain number of terminals and each terminal represents a subsystem including waterfront structures, operating cranes, and electric power systems.

The main features of this approach are hereinafter briefly described, while further details can be found in Conca et al. (2020).

The simplified representation of the port system of Gioia Tauro includes the following vulnerable elements:

- waterfront structures where port operations of cargo handling take place;
- cargo handling components, i.e. cranes;
- elements of the electric power system;
- terminals, including the previously listed port elements.

Interdependencies among these port elements are modelled in the simulation-based methodology that is graphically represented in Figure 3-16 and briefly described as follows:

- Cranes/waterfront: a crane may result in out of service because of the damage experienced by the waterfront structure (wharf) along which it usually works during cargo handling.
- Cranes/electric power system: if a crane is not powered by electric energy (and the crane does not have a backup power supply), it cannot be in service.
- Terminal/waterfront and cranes: if the waterfront structures of a terminal are damaged (i.e. the terminal is considered out of service if at least 75% of the total length of the structures are damaged) or no active cranes are present, the terminal cannot be used for port handling operations.

Figure 3-16: Graphical representation of the functionality loss model adopted for TB5 able to address the interdependencies among port components within the simulation-based framework developed at EUCENTRE (modified from Bozzoni et al., 2018 and Conca et al., 2020).

The vulnerability of strategic seaport components, such as wharves, cranes, and electric power units, can be assessed using fragility models. Further details on this topic can be found in Deliverable 4.2 of TURNkey project (2021) in the section focusing on TB5.

Outcomes obtained from the fragility curves are the damage states (DS) for each component. The following rules are adopted to evaluate the functionality of port elements:

- An electric power unit is operative if its DS is lower than moderate, i.e. minor or null.
- A crane is in service if its DS is lower than moderate, if the DS of the waterfront on which it is installed is lower than moderate, and if the DS of the electric power unit that powers the crane is lower than moderate.
- A terminal is in service if it has at least one operating crane and if the DS of at least 25% of the total length of the waterfront structure that composes the terminal is lower than moderate.

Container throughput is widely adopted as a measure of the performance of a container port, thus the performance of a multi-component port system is measured by using the performance indicator, which represent the containers that the system can handle in a pre-defined time frame, i.e. the volume of containers, measured by means of twenty-foot equivalent unit (TEU, a standard measure for a container for transporting goods), handled in 24hr. In the simulation-based framework herein adopted, the PI is calculated in each scenario starting from the level of functionality of each port element. It is computed with reference to a terminal i by using the following formula:

$$PI_{Terminal_i} = \sum_k CraneCapacity_k \quad (3-12)$$

where $CraneCapacity_k$ is the capacity of the crane k of each terminal, measured in TEU/day. The results for each terminal are summed up to obtain a PI for all the terminals:

$$PI = \sum_i PI_{Terminal_i} \quad (3-13)$$

At the end of the simulations, a mean value of PI is computed as

$$PI_m = \frac{\sum_n PI_n}{N} \quad (3-14)$$

where N is the total number of simulations and PI_n is the PI of the scenario n . The performance loss is estimated as:

$$Loss = \frac{PI_{ordinary} - PI_m}{PI_{ordinary}} \cdot 100 \quad (3-15)$$

where $PI_{ordinary}$ is the PI computed for all the port elements in service.

In each simulation (or scenario), a Monte Carlo analysis is used to sample the value of the seismic parameters from the associated probabilistic distributions to be used as intensity measures for the fragility functions. The physical damage of all of the components is then sampled from the fragility functions. Based on the sampled damage state of the single component in each scenario, the functionality of the port elements is evaluated. The functionality relies on not only the direct damage to the elements but also the damage suffered by the elements as a result of the interconnected components. At the end of the simulation, the results are calculated in terms of system performance and amount of loss. The system performance of each scenario is measured by the PI. Moreover, the functionality loss levels are computed for those components whose functionality in the event of an earthquake is jeopardized by the damage state of other elements (i.e., cranes and wharf structures) and is defined as the probability for an element to end up out of service after the ground shaking. This procedure is repeated several times until the process converges toward stable results (achieved when the moving average of the PI converges to a constant) to fully characterize the uncertainty represented by the probability distributions of the input parameters and of the fragility models adopted for the port elements.

3.6 TB-6: Groningen Province, Netherlands [DEL, KNMI]

3.6.1 Brief description of the Test Bed

In the gas field of Groningen, a province in the North of the Netherlands, the earthquake activity has increased in the last years as a result of gas extraction. TB-6 focuses on the impact of induced seismicity on the existing buildings and infrastructures. In particular, the elements exposed to the seismic risk that have been considered are bridges, viaducts, underpasses, buildings and sluices.

In particular eight lock-complexes have been selected by the local authority as critical infrastructures potentially affected by the earthquake events.

Each lock complex connects river channels in the Groningen province with different water levels between the upstream and downstream sides. Their function is to allow the navigation and the transportation of goods and persons in the province, where ships can move through channels with different water levels. The sluices are constructed in dikes, so they must guarantee the safety against flooding, which is a requirement for the dikes. Based on the data available, the locks are composed of two gates, one at each side of the lock, and retaining structures along the sides next to the dikes. The structures are generally founded on piles.

Drawings of some of the structures are available together with some site-investigation data (e.g. boreholes and CPT logs). The data of material properties, e.g. the reinforced concrete and the amount of steel in the sections, as well as the pile length is often missing. In some cases, the type of piles is known (e.g. wooden piles in Groevesuice or steel piles in Jan B. Bronssluis), in other cases such information is missing. The length of the piles is also sometimes not known.

The functionality models selected for each element at risk are summarized in the following section.

Figure 3-17: Location of the sluices in Groningen

3.6.2 Functionality loss models at component level

3.6.2.1 For the bridges, viaducts and underpasses

The functionality model defined for TB2 can be used for TB6. The fragility functions used in TB2 are defined for 4 damage states (i.e. DS0 – intact; DS1 – minor damage; DS2 – moderate damage and DS3 – major damage). On the contrary, the fragility functions for the bridges, viaducts and underpasses described in Table 3.15, Table 3.16 and Table 3.17 of deliverable report D4.2 (Faravelli et al., 2021) for TB6 are defined for 2 classes: a damage limit state (SLD) and collapse limit state (SLC). For this reason, for what concerns the functionality model, the class SLD and SLC can be seen as DS1 and DS3, respectively. This shows that 100% loss of functionality is considered for SLC, which seems a reasonable estimation for the rapid response after the earthquake event. Further analyses of local repairing capabilities are needed to assess the model performance during the recovery phase. These are presented in deliverable 5.2

3.6.2.2 For buildings

In the database of SERA, the location of houses is lumped for each municipality. There is no information for example, of the location of the house and the surrounding road. Therefore, it is impossible to quantify the risk connected to the collapse of individual buildings and the loss of accessibility of roads obstructed by their debris. For this reason the approach outlined for TB2 will also be adopted here.

3.6.2.3 For sluices

- Study of failure mechanisms

The identification of the potential failure mechanisms is the first step to determine the fragility/functionality of the lock system after an earthquake event. The study of Deltares (Deltares report, 2017) illustrates possible failure mechanisms which can occur in sluices located in the north side of the Eemskanaal, a channel in the Groningen province. This study can be used as a general framework for all sluices in Groningen.

Five construction types are identified, which are illustrated in the Table 3-2 and Table 3-3. For each construction type, three type of failures are distinguished: failure by loss of stability, failure of a single construction component, and failure by soil compaction and settlement. It is worth noticing that a single lock complex can have multiple construction types, so it can be susceptible to different failure mechanisms depending on the part of the structure which is considered.

Table 3-2 failure mechanisms of the water retaining structures of the sluices of Northern side Eemskanaal. (Part A) (Deltares report, 2017)

	Failure by sliding in the soil (A)	Failure of construction or piles (B)	Failure of dike (dike height) by settlement due to compaction or squeezing (C)
1. Soil around the construction	a) b) global failure 		
2. U-construction on raft or piled foundation	Not applicable	a) failure of concrete construction 	
3. L-wall on piles with retaining sheet pile wall	a) failure passive resistance 		

	Failure by sliding in the soil (A)	Failure of construction or piles (B)	Failure of dike (dike height) by settlement due to compaction or squeezing (C)
1. Soil around the construction	a) b) global failure 		
		g) compaction intermediate sand layer leads to settlement sheet pile wall 	

Table 3-3: failure mechanisms of the water retaining structures of the sluices of Northern side Eemskanaal. (Part B) (Deltares report, 2017)

	Failure by sliding in the soil (A)	Failure of construction or piles (B)	Failure of dike (dike height) by settlement due to compaction or squeezing (C)
4. Cut-off wall below the lock head	Not applicable	a) failure of pile connection b) failure connection cut-off wall by compaction intermediate sand layer 	Not applicable
5. Sluice doors	Not applicable	a) Failure of sluice doors 	b) settlement of sluice doors due to settlement of construction (settlement of sluice door = settlement construction)

- The case study of “Groevesluis”.

Based on the geographical location of the sluices in the Groningen province and the seismic hazard, the lock complex “Groevesluis” is selected for an in-depth investigation. The “Groevesluis” lock complex has two

sluices, on the north and on the south side of the Eemskanaal. The top view of the sluice, located on the south side of Eemskanaal, is illustrated in Figure 3-19

Figure 3-18: Location of the lock complex “Groevesluis” (north and south) along the channel “Eemskanaal”.

Figure 3-19: top view of the Groevesluice south.

This lock complex (the Groevesluice south) forms a connection between the Eemskanaal and the Schildmeer, called the Groeve. The Groeve, formerly also Schildgroeve or Damstermaar, is a canal in the province of Groningen that runs from the Schildmeer to Appingedam. Originally it served for the drainage of the lake to the Damsterdiep. However, the construction of the Eemskanaal (1866 - 1876) has rendered the section between this canal and the Damsterdiep superfluous. From then on, this part of De Groeve was only important for shipping. Due to the difference in level on the Eemskanaal and that of the Groeve, a lock was required in both the northern and southern parts of the Groeve.

The original year of construction of the lock is 1963. The lock walls and the lock heads are found on wooden piles. Two cross sections are illustrated in Figure 3-20 taken at the centre of the sluice and at the sluice head on the Schildmeer side. The central section is composed of two L-shape walls supported by piles with retaining structure underneath. The bottom of the sluice consists of a thin concrete floor between the wooden sheet piles under the lock walls. The sections of the lock heads (Figure 3-20) consist of U-shaped constructions of reinforced concrete. The lock doors have been replaced with steel ones in 2011.

Figure 3-20: Two cross sections of the sluice. (a) at the centre of the sluice; (b) at the sluice head on the Schildmeer side.

Drawings of the structure are available together with some site-investigation data performed before the construction of the locks. However, the data of material properties, e.g. the strength of the concrete and the amount of steel in the sections, as well as the pile length is missing. Therefore, some of the failure mechanisms cannot be calculated, e.g. the failure of structural components like piles, concrete construction or entrance doors. Further investigation is needed to determine the strength of the materials which allows to complete this study. One of the mechanisms that is investigated in this study is the failure of the wooden retaining wall (see Figure 3-20a) induced by liquefaction-induced settlements of intermediate sand layers, which are located along the pile length. The settlement of the sand layers leads to movement of the retaining wall which could lead to possible loss of connection between the construction and the retaining wall. The consequences of this mechanism are the stability loss of the system and potential piping, which lead to functionality loss of the sluice and loss of flooding protection. The settlements are induced by the densification of the sand layers after liquefaction occurs.

○ Liquefaction assessment and surface settlement

Three CPT logs are available along the sluice. The soil profile has a relatively shallow loosely packed sand layers, which can lead to liquefaction during a seismic event. For this reason, a CPT-based Groningen-specific liquefaction assessment (Green et. al., 2018) is performed using the Monte Carlo approach for the in-situ CPT logs available around the sluice. In the CPT1 and 3, two layers are identified (L1 and L2, shallower and deeper respectively). In the CPT2, only a single layer is detected. The liquefaction assessment includes uncertainties in the cone resistance, liquefaction triggering curve, magnitude scaling factor and in the depth-stress reduction factor. As expected, probability of liquefaction in the layer increases with the PGA, and it is generally higher in shallower layers compared to the deeper ones.

Figure 3-21: probability of liquefaction in the sand layer as function of PGA.

The surface settlement was then computed following the method of Ishihara and Yoshimine (1992), which correlates volumetric strains induced in the sand layer with the factor of safety against liquefaction. The results of the most conservative location (i.e. CPT3, where the largest expected settlement occur in the thick shallow sand layer) are shown in Figure 3-21. In all other CPTs, the probability of a settlement larger than 5 cm is very low.

Figure 3-22: Probability of surface settlement greater than a value as function of PGA. The values are specified in the legend.

o Damage assessment

The soil settlement, as per se, does not necessarily induce damage if the connection between the wooden sheet pile wall and the lock walls is strong and long enough. However, the details of such a connection are not known. It can be reasonably assumed that the length of interpenetration can be in the order of 5 cm. It can be that some friction prevents relative displacements if the settlement is lower than 10 cm, otherwise the loss of connection occurs.

The loss of connection induces only a local damage since the retaining structure tends to move inside the sluice, as the soil is not supported. Piping or seepage flow does not occur in this case since the retaining structure is surrounded by low-permeable soils (i.e. clay and peat).

Liquefaction can also induce global instability of the entire structure, as illustrated in Table 3-2(case 3-A), where a slip surface develops and soil flows inside the sluice. This failure mechanism occurs only in case of a cross section with L-shape walls (Figure 3-20a). In this case, a 2D finite element analyses is performed for the condition of post-seismic stability where all sand layers are assumed to be fully-liquefied with a liquefied undrained shear strength (Idriss and Boulanger, 2008). In absence of detailed soil data, the strength parameters for clay and peat are estimated using NEN 9997-1+C2:2017, with reference to soft peat and soft clay which is a conservative assumption. The available old CPTs cannot be used to obtain soil parameters in those layers, as they are not reliable for such a low cone resistance. The cross section, based on CPT2 located in the centre of the sluice, is found to be stable even though with a factor of safety slightly higher than 1. It is worth mentioning that the analysis does not include the additional strength carried by the large number of piles immersed into the soil.

o Functionality of the sluice

Despite the lack of data, this study shows an attempt to quantify the effect of seismic event on the “Groevesluis” south lock complex. With respect to the considered failure mechanisms and available data, the functionality of the sluice seems to be not severely affected. Only in case of PGA greater than approximately 0.15g, a soil settlement can induce a lack of connection of the wooden sheet pile wall, which can be repaired

in the order of few weeks, not necessarily right after the seismic event as no significant seepage flow/piping is expected.

The sluice located on the north side of the Eemskanaal has a similar structure characteristics and soil profile to the “Groevesluis” south. It follows that the conclusions found for the south sluice are valid also for the north one.

- Assessment of other sluices

- Jan B. Bronssluis

The cross section of the “Jan B. Bronssluis” is a U-shape continuous retaining structure founded on steel piles. The structure is surrounded by clay and peat layers and the piles are founded on sandy soil. For this sluice, the possible failure mechanism is the settlement of the entire structure in case of the full liquefaction of the sand layer, which are located approximately 9-10 m below the surface. Even though liquefaction can occur in those deep sandy soils in case of $PGA > 0.12g$, it is very unlikely that large settlements occur. In conclusion, the chance to have functionality problem is very low for this sluice.

- Dorkwerdersluis, Oostersluis and Driewegsluis

The location of these sluices is far from the most hazardous area. The expected seismic loading is low compared to other sluices, therefore the chance to have functionality issue is very low for these sluices.

- Slochtersluis and Zeesluizen Farmsum

Lack of data prevents a proper functionality assessment for these sluices.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The objective of the present deliverable is to establish the body of knowledge necessary for the development of predictive models for the vulnerability and loss estimation of exposed assets. This encompasses both physical vulnerability of single elements, as well as the systemic vulnerability and functionality loss of interconnected infrastructure, due to the importance of the latter when conducting rapid response operations. The ultimate objective is to improve existing models with a focus on simplicity and applicability for various types of exposure data and to harmonise the input-output data for use on the TURNkey FWCR platform.

A broad review of the state of the art has been undertaken amounting to in excess of 150 sources to determine the remit of current models and their applicability to the EU context in terms of providing supporting information for rapid response. Such literature review has encompassed models for a) ordinary buildings, b) localised building infrastructure, such as hospitals and schools; c) linear infrastructure such as road network and railway network, with particular attention to their critical assets, i.e. bridges; d) highly differentiated and hierarchical infrastructure such as ports facilities and e) waterway infrastructure, specifically sluices and locks. The focus on such assets is strictly linked to requirements of the test beds.

The literature reviewed covers both function to compute direct and indirect losses and functionality loss functions. While most of the available models cover losses (economic or social) for individual buildings, functionality loss models are available for road networks and hospitals, with some emerging models for schools.

For road networks there is a wealth of literature on fragility functions of bridges and on the resilience of road network system. However models specifically quantifying the functionality losses and the repair time, considering real case scenarios are still few and of limited applicability. In the TURNkey project these have been extensively reviewed and tested with respect to TB2. Ultimately the model developed by Gehl & D'Ayala, 2018; Shinozuka et al., 2003 is applied for the computation of the functional loss of bridges, while Argyroudis et al 2010 is used for the computation of the debris caused by collapsed buildings affecting roadways. On the basis of these models then a bespoke agent-based model is adopted to explore different recovery strategies and their associated recovery time for the entire network, while a Bayesian updating framework is adopted in order to account for observations gathered from the field. The two models interact to provide optimal decision making for rapid response. This work is further presented in Deliverable 4.8.

The framework developed for TB2 in terms of computation of road network functionality loss and recovery is also applicable to TB1 and TB6. For TB1 the specific repair capacity at the site and the effects on emergency services delivery need to be further explored.

The loss of functionality of hospitals is relevant to TB1 and TB2. Relevant models available in literature cover both loss of functionality of the physical infrastructure and loss of availability of personnel. For TB1, of particular interest is the loss of functionality of the Emergency Department to ensure the prompt emergency response at urban level. The model that appears to be most appropriate and applicable given the availability of data and scale of the analysis is the World Health Organization & Pan American Health, (2015) model, which provide a Hospital Safety Index by scoring a set of parameters. A tool proposed in D5.2 will use an adapted version of the approach adopted by World Health Organization & Pan American Health Organization (2015) to assess the loss and resilience of infrastructures located in the other TBs.

Schools represent a second type of localised critical infrastructure, usually composed of a single or number of buildings with different function and sometimes architecture and structural fragility. Most studies cover physical fragility and vulnerability, and often identify strengthening and upgrading measures, relevant to much of the EU school portfolio, which is generally quite aged. However very few studies consider functionality

losses. Among these Hassan et al. (2020) propose a method that includes also the “soft” component of the infrastructure “school”, i.e. the human resources, and functionality is evaluated considering a “success tree” approach. Within TURNkey some of the indicators used in this study will be included in one of the CIs assessment tools proposed in D5.2 and tested in the testbeds.

For ordinary buildings an extensive review of fragility and vulnerability models has been compiled in deliverable 4.2 and a specific model for attribution of damage given a shake map has been presented in D4.1. In this deliverable a number of models have been considered to establish their applicability in relation to the Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE) needs and actions within the TURNkey platform. The studies are classified according to the studied building types, building use, inputs, outputs, and applicability to testbeds. In general loss functions/models are not directly applicable because of the missing link with measured data (e.g. PGA) in the context of rapid response analysis. The input in many of the models available is related to the building response (e.g. inter-storey drift), and a link between the building response and the ground motion parameters is needed. Not all building types are represented and therefore specific modelling at testbeds would be required. Many studies focusing on losses provide these in terms of expected annual loss or lifecycle costs, which however are not relevant in terms of RRE, where a relationship between damage state and loss of function is needed. In terms of applicability to the TURNkey platform Kappos et al. (1998) and Kappos & Dimitrakopoulos (2008) are considered directly applicable. However calibration between damage grades, mean damage ratio ranges and mean loss ratio is needed. These functions are applied at a macroscale for cases where exposure data is available at the scale of the urban block. In the TB more refined approaches might be needed, for instance when determining the interaction between damaged building debris and functionality loss of road network.

In TB3 which deals with building losses of two municipalities in Iceland, damage and loss model, obtained from surveys of past damaging events and valid at the local scale are used in modelling vulnerability, damage, economic losses and recovery transition at community and infrastructure level. These models are presented in detail in D5.2.

For railways the focus within TURNkey is on individual critical assets, such as bridges, rather than system analysis. Loss of functionality in this case is mainly related to derailment problem due to loss of alignments of the rails. In TURNkey, the derailment problem is handled through multiparameter limit states paired with engineering demand parameters (see Guillaud 2006). Early warning actions maximizing railway bridge functionality and other consequences are established through fragility functions defining failure/survival conditioned to the intensity measure (Shinozuka et al. 2000), consequence models expressing costs and benefits of relevant actions (Cremen et al. 2020), decision analysis for the optimal risk-based action (analogous to Kameshwar et al. 2020), and assessing the system’s contributions via the Value of Information (Wu et al. 2013). The proposed formulation is applied on a railway bridge in Luchon region at the French-Spanish border as part of the Testbed 2, with the aims of quantifying the early warning benefits in terms of various consequences such as downtime, casualties, and monetary losses under various derailment scenarios.

The literature on ports is very specific and given the multi-component nature of the port system, the potential disruption of one component may trigger a domino (or cascade) effect that influences the performance of the entire system. In this respect a specific model has been developed within the TURNkey project for application to the Gioia Tauro test bed (Conca et al 2020).

The literature on canal ways component or system fragility to earthquake is substantially non-existent. Therefore bespoke liquefaction and settlement failure curves have been developed within TURNkey, in recognition that these two phenomena will affect the functionality of the sluice and their repairability.

It can be concluded that either generic or specific functionality loss models have been identified for each of the systems studied within the TB and that such models are suitable to provide relevant information on

accessibility and use of system in the immediate aftermath of earthquakes and their effect on rapid response. It has also been shown that the same model can be suitable for different TBS. Nonetheless further work within TURNkey is needed in the following 12 month to properly harmonise these models where possible across different sector of the infrastructure and to provide reference functionality loss curve to the TURNkey platform which can be reliably used in future applications beyond the end of the project. This work will form part of WP6.

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5 APPENDIX I: LIST OF VULNERABLE COMPONENTS FOR THE RDN SYSTEM STUDIED IN TB-2

Table 5-1: List of bridges and corresponding fragility models (from report D4.2), in the Luchon Valley RDN. The bridge ID corresponds to the ID of the edge where each bridge is located.

ID	Longitude	Latitude	μ_1 [g]	β_1	μ_2 [g]	β_2	μ_3 [g]	β_3
545	0.7481005	42.8623665	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
546	0.7357005	42.8492065	0.79	0.787	1.524	1.518	2.879	2.867
2	0.6918775	42.915652	0.11	0.02	0.2	0.05	0.3	0.08
486	0.64737	42.9728235	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
527	0.714911	42.8838145	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
529	0.71742	42.8817065	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
482	0.636202	42.985605	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
480	0.6323495	42.989788	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
476	0.630651	42.9933995	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
242	0.639766	42.9661535	0.575	0.328	0.656	0.374	0.932	0.531
457	0.6430005	42.953039	1.166	1.123	1.61	1.551	2.846	2.74
459	0.642823	42.952594	1.166	1.123	1.61	1.551	2.846	2.74
525	0.699634	42.8959975	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
478	0.6275915	42.991163	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
467	0.655285	42.9276035	1.166	1.123	1.61	1.551	2.846	2.74
497	0.654023	42.929707	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
495	0.651228	42.9344335	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
493	0.6491275	42.9379845	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
499	0.68226	42.9238455	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
454	0.7419015	42.8672495	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
533	0.7468165	42.866354	0.79	0.787	1.524	1.518	2.879	2.867
505	0.6907795	42.9102335	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
501	0.692208	42.9123625	0.99	1.019	1.263	1.3	2.354	2.423
503	0.694663	42.9115825	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
549	0.630572	42.8992925	0.09	0.02	0.2	0.05	0.25	0.07
554	0.6217445	42.895197	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
557	0.6201025	42.8900685	0.09	0.02	0.2	0.05	0.25	0.07
675	0.548263	42.8254665	0.15	0.03	0.32	0.08	0.45	0.23
531	0.6607125	42.9682	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
488	0.6446705	42.9572735	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
516	0.6474025	42.917373	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
662	0.486378	42.7928165	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
614	0.6032045	42.7728535	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
616	0.603537	42.7721635	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
619	0.608748	42.75361	0.79	0.787	1.524	1.518	2.879	2.867
603	0.608234	42.8029475	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
605	0.608965	42.7959585	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429

601	0.6031495	42.805896	0.79	0.787	1.524	1.518	2.879	2.867
591	0.6038065	42.8377755	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
661	0.505596	42.7953055	0.15	0.03	0.32	0.08	0.45	0.23
647	0.565141	42.8010795	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
649	0.5631835	42.802811	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
629	0.610161	42.7449205	0.15	0.03	0.32	0.08	0.45	0.23
631	0.608483	42.7447405	0.15	0.03	0.32	0.08	0.45	0.23
633	0.581132	42.748674	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
635	0.5736835	42.7485435	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
621	0.614449	42.741683	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
624	0.6155205	42.7403685	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
625	0.6501375	42.719516	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
627	0.653524	42.721322	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
562	0.6141835	42.877914	0.575	0.328	0.656	0.374	0.932	0.531
306	0.6164245	42.885484	0.09	0.02	0.2	0.05	0.25	0.07
607	0.5967875	42.794336	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
650	0.560939	42.8064945	0.16	0.03	0.27	0.07	0.45	0.23
609	0.5928985	42.7938305	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
507	0.697997	42.909176	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
521	0.710659	42.8959725	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
523	0.7267285	42.892472	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
658	0.5149595	42.80843	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
565	0.612961	42.875768	0.99	1.019	1.263	1.3	2.354	2.423
567	0.6082225	42.876291	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
555	0.6157145	42.8969575	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
517	0.63919	42.9149465	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
655	0.523586	42.8032585	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
656	0.5219975	42.804693	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
653	0.532401	42.8058405	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
583	0.602605	42.8528515	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
580	0.60411	42.8646035	0.15	0.03	0.32	0.08	0.45	0.23
491	0.6473105	42.9387765	0.79	0.787	1.524	1.518	2.879	2.867
667	0.4879405	42.814201	0.15	0.03	0.32	0.08	0.45	0.23
668	0.4726025	42.810975	0.15	0.03	0.32	0.08	0.45	0.23
671	0.4718455	42.8075535	0.19	0.05	0.3	0.07	0.53	0.17
597	0.603765	42.82876	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
110	0.6011515	42.828666	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
470	0.6018815	42.828685	0.11	0.02	0.18	0.04	0.3	0.07
595	0.6021505	42.8318895	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
593	0.603212	42.835588	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
612	0.598704	42.7827745	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
673	0.4692045	42.801933	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
263	0.7344165	42.872903	0.09	0.02	0.2	0.05	0.25	0.07
618	0.620848	42.76964	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669

688	0.5188205	42.852494	0.15	0.03	0.32	0.08	0.45	0.23
687	0.5230805	42.850811	0.09	0.02	0.2	0.05	0.25	0.07
685	0.52864	42.8466915	0.09	0.02	0.2	0.05	0.25	0.07
682	0.5395645	42.8437145	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
681	0.550471	42.8359975	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
679	0.5505075	42.8345415	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
676	0.550554	42.8300095	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
575	0.606288	42.866115	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
569	0.612568	42.8665145	0.15	0.03	0.32	0.08	0.45	0.23
573	0.6082925	42.868759	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
512	0.8070315	42.9326595	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
508	0.804543	42.92101	0.15	0.03	0.32	0.08	0.45	0.23
510	0.8030345	42.921636	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
645	0.5863005	42.7606285	0.16	0.03	0.27	0.07	0.45	0.23
643	0.5813115	42.7505585	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
641	0.580247	42.750791	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
639	0.574208	42.750342	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
637	0.5723665	42.7495615	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
535	0.750375	42.866554	0.28	1.3	0.45	0.23	0.82	0.31
484	0.6596405	42.9819075	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
547	0.628191	42.9050025	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
514	0.6426545	42.9243465	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
537	0.780903	42.874515	0.09	0.02	0.2	0.05	0.25	0.07
539	0.7820695	42.87493	0.09	0.02	0.2	0.05	0.25	0.07
540	0.7867705	42.8714765	0.09	0.02	0.2	0.05	0.25	0.07
543	0.7980885	42.865334	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
610	0.599499	42.7913475	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
519	0.658803	42.9136235	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
571	0.609637	42.8681695	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
473	0.609411	42.8675825	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
577	0.606916	42.86559	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
665	0.5088335	42.80991	0.669	0.271	0.755	0.306	1.057	0.429
464	0.644899	42.9126395	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
462	0.644784	42.912142	0.11	0.02	0.18	0.04	0.3	0.07
585	0.622411	42.8526715	0.16	0.03	0.27	0.07	0.45	0.23
587	0.611486	42.8450865	1.447	0.897	1.753	1.086	2.694	1.669
589	0.6058135	42.8382605	0.15	0.03	0.32	0.08	0.45	0.23

Table 5-2: List of road segments (edges) that are potentially blocked by buildings debris. The polygon ID refers to the group of buildings that have been manually identified in the BL area (see Figure 3-7).

Polygon ID	Edge ID (Vulnerable Road)	Nb buildings
1	419	28

2	420	7
3	415	4
4	415	3
5	415	10
7	415	21
8	415	27
9	415	16
10	415	24
11	412	18
12	412	40
13	418	46
15	407	69
14	407	19
16	59	14
17	360	20
18	608	45
20	608	9
19	414	40
21	413	11
22	363	12
23	361	37
28	361	2
24	365	38
6	364	11
25	299	17
26	159	23
27	159	3